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*A Comparative Analysis of Types of Proceedings in the
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A Comparative Analysis of Types of Proceedings in the German Federal Constitutional Court

By Luisa Wendel*, Anna Shadrova**, & Alexander Tischbirek*** ‡

Abstract

Quantitative approaches are gaining in popularity in German legal research and analysis of large corpora of legal text may be supported by text mining methods. We employ topic modeling, which aims at retrieving the ‘topics’ of a corpus, to identify words that relate to certain areas of law present in the case-law of the German Federal Constitutional Court (FCC). These are then evaluated by legal experts and used to show that there are significant content-related differences between the two most frequent types of proceedings before the FCC. Technical and somewhat instable areas of law, such as tax law, social law, and civil service law, are significantly overrepresented in referrals for judicial review; whereas areas of law, which are characterized by well-developed case law and judicial doctrine, appear significantly more often in constitutional complaints. This insight may come as a surprise, since the Court’s material scope of review is basically identical in both types of proceedings. Our considerations do not, however, seem to apply to private law. Keeping some methodological and epistemological concerns regarding the heuristic nature of topic modeling in mind, the study exemplifies its productive use in complementing, rather than replacing, more traditional techniques of analysis in legal studies.

A. Introduction

Jurisprudence in Germany is traditionally conceived as a hermeneutic science rarely using empirical, let alone quantitative methods.¹ It focuses on individual texts – particularly statutes, regulations and court decisions – which are subject to “close reading” in order to answer research questions. In so far as one might consider court decisions as empirical evidence of the application of a statute, it is often not possible to look at all relevant decisions. Instead, the researcher will have to limit her research to a subset, not

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‡ Project ‘Leibniz Linguistic Research into Constitutional Law’ (<https://www.lehrstuhl-moellers.de/en/hauptnavigation/llcon> - last visited Aug 26, 2021), chaired by Prof. Dr. Christoph Möllers, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Faculty of Law, graciously funded through the Leibniz prize program of the German Research Foundation (DFG). We would also like to thank Ali Ighreiz and Nils Weinberg, who were of great help in the conceptualization of this paper.

¹ KRISTIAN KÜHL, HERMANN REICHOLD and MICHAEL RONELLENFITSCH, *EINFÜHRUNG IN DIE RECHTSWISSENSCHAFT* (3rd ed. 2019), § 1 at 62: “Rechtswissenschaftler [...] nutzen keine Statistiken, falsifizieren keine Hypothesen.” (“Legal scholars [...] do not use statistics, do not falsify hypotheses.”)

necessarily based on a random sample. The choice of material may be restricted by the availability of the material² or it may follow considerations of importance arrived at by other researchers or practice³.

While a researcher may focus on the magnitudes in which the phenomena of interest occur, e.g. in determining which of various interpretations of a legal norm is being supported by a majority of courts, exact counting traditionally plays a less significant role. As far as the interpretation of statutes is concerned, the (perceived) persuasiveness of an argument is considered to be relevant, not its frequency. However, studies employing quantitative methods in order to reach (more) empirically substantiated conclusions about courts' behavior appear to become more popular in recent years.⁴ These are usually based on a manual classification of the relevant phenomena carried out by legal scholars. Provided that intersubjectively comprehensible guidelines for annotation exist, this may ensure that the counted phenomena can withstand assessment by other experts. Manual coding, however, is expensive in terms of personnel and time and may again result in a limitation of the amount of documents that can be considered in the study. This calls for the (supporting) use of computer-assisted methods.

These include the automated search for keywords or for text passages that follow more complex rules as well as machine-learning algorithms based on statistical calculations. The term *data mining*⁵ or, more specifically, *text mining* subsumes various procedures for the analysis of data / text which may, in principle, be applied to help answer research questions in legal studies. Their application without a clear starting hypothesis, however, harbors the risk of arbitrary retrospective interpretation.⁶ Furthermore, a text mining algorithm's way of decision-making may not be entirely comprehensible for human experts, which may impair the intersubjective communication of results.

In this paper, we introduce a possible method for analyzing a larger corpus of court decisions by using a text mining procedure as a preparatory step and having its results evaluated by legal experts before using them to answer specific research questions. In doing so, we analyze the thematic composition of about 3.300 decisions by the German Federal Constitutional Court (FCC, *Bundesverfassungsgericht*, *BVerfG*), which are the result of the two most frequent types of proceedings (constitutional complaint and referral for judicial review) and which have been published in the Official Report Series⁷. The data is published as a corpus and publicly available.⁸

First, we will give a short introduction to text mining and specifically topic modeling and its previous application in legal research (section B). After an introduction into German Constitutional Procedure and its most frequent types of proceedings, which inspired our hypotheses, we will embark on a topic-modeling-

² Lower court judgments, in particular, are not widely available in Germany, see Hanjo Hamann, *Der blinde Fleck der deutschen Rechtswissenschaft?*, 76 JURISTENZEITUNG 656–665 (2021).

³ See Ali Ighreiz, Christoph Möllers, Louis Rolfes, et al., *Karlsruher Kanones?*, 145 ARCHIV DES ÖFFENTLICHEN RECHTS (2020) 537–613.

⁴ Examples in the field of constitutional law include analyses of argument types in the German Federal Constitutional Courts' (FCC) decisions: NIELS PETERSEN, VERHÄLTNISSMÄSSIGKEIT ALS RATIONALITÄTSKONTROLLE: EINE RECHTSEMPIRISCHE STUDIE VERFASSUNGSGERICHTLICHER RECHTSPRECHUNG ZU DEN FREIHEITSGRUNDRECHTEN (2015); of comparative law arguments in FCC decisions: STEFAN MARTINI: VERGLEICHENDE VERFASSUNGSRECHTSPRECHUNG: PRAXIS, VIABILITÄT UND BEGRÜNDUNG RECHTSVERGLEICHENDER ARGUMENTATION DURCH VERFASSUNGSGERICHTE (2018); of the structure and context of the application of the principle of proportionality in FCC decisions: Andrej Lang, *Der Verhältnismäßigkeitsgrundsatz in der Rechtsprechung des Bundesverfassungsgerichts: Eine rechtsempirische Untersuchung mit rechtsvergleichenden Perspektiven*, 145 ARCHIV DES ÖFFENTLICHEN RECHTS (2020) 75 and of argument types in constitutional and administrative courts' decisions on legislation aiming to prevent the spread of COVID-19: Anika Klafki, *Kontingenz des Rechts in der Krise: Rechtsempirische Analyse gerichtlicher Argumentationsmuster in der Corona-Pandemie*, 69 Jahrbuch des öffentlichen Rechts (2021), 583.

⁵ For an introduction see, for example: CHARU C. AGGARWAL, DATA MINING: THE TEXTBOOK (2015).

⁶ Anna Shadrova, Topic models do not model topics: epistemological remarks and steps towards best practices (in press), *Journal of Data Mining and Digital Humanities*.

⁷ Entscheidungen des Bundesverfassungsgerichts, according to § 31 (1) of the Rules of Procedure of the Federal Constitutional Court (*Geschäftsordnung des Bundesverfassungsgerichts*, *GO-BVerfG*) and also known as "*Amtliche Sammlung*".

⁸ Möllers, Christoph, Shadrova, Anna, and Wendel, Luisa (2021), *BVerfGE-Korpus (1.0)* [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4551408>. Note that the present study only uses decisions pronounced until 2017.

assisted inquiry into the subject matters that characterize constitutional complaints on the one hand and referrals for judicial review on the other hand (section C). We finish with a conclusion (section D).

B. Topic Modeling and its Application to Legal Research

Text mining can make use of machine learning methods that may either be supervised or unsupervised.⁹ Supervised methods require training data in the form of manually labeled data. If, for example, text is to be sorted into fixed categories (*classification*), these categories have to be decided on and related to a certain amount of data points in order to train a classifier that may then classify new, unseen text. Unsupervised methods, on the other hand, do not require human decisions on categories and can use information inherent in the texts in order to assign them to one of several clusters (*clustering*). Topic modeling is an example of an unsupervised method.

I. Topic Modeling

Topic modeling algorithms are statistical text mining or information retrieval methods used for uncovering the main themes underlying a collection of documents, their connection to each other and their development over time.¹⁰ Different models and algorithms exist, the most widely used at present being latent Dirichlet allocation (LDA).¹¹ LDA is built on the presumption that all documents in the collection share the same original set of topics, but each document may concern these topics in different proportions,¹² so that only a selection of these topics will appear in the document. A topic is defined as a “distribution over a fixed vocabulary”.¹³ Each word in the vocabulary for a given topic is assigned a probability of appearing in a document about this topic, where probabilities sum up to one for each topic.¹⁴ Topics are assumed to be static and fixed before any document is written. This means that topics cannot evolve to contain new words in later texts (such as would be expected of historical progress, where for example the present-day discourse around the European Union will contain different words compared to the European Coal and Steel Community), and topics cannot merge or split over time either.

The creation process for each document is assumed to consist of two steps.¹⁵ First, a distribution over topics is randomly chosen. In other words, the topics about which the document is being written and the proportions of the document reserved for these topics are determined. Secondly, for each word in the document, a topic from said distribution is randomly chosen and the word itself is randomly chosen from the distribution over the vocabulary corresponding to this topic. It follows that the order of words is not considered to be of importance. In reality, of course, documents are not being created in a random process.

Topic models aim at discovering these “hidden structures” – the topics underlying both the whole corpus and the individual documents as well as the weights of words within a certain topic. The model first randomly assigns words to topics and topics to documents, then shuffles them until a maximization condition is met.¹⁶ In general, no annotations or metadata are required, although some topic models may

⁹ On this distinction: Charu C. Aggarwal & ChengXiang Zhai, An Introduction to Text Mining, in *MINING TEXT DATA* (Charu C. Aggarwal & ChengXiang Zhai, eds., 2012), at 5-6.

¹⁰ David M. Blei, *Probabilistic Topic Models*, 55 *COMMUNICATIONS OF THE ACM* 77–84 (2012), DOI: 10.1145/2133806.2133826.

¹¹ Blei, *supra* note 10, at 78.

¹² Blei, *supra* note 10, at 79.

¹³ Blei, *supra* note 10, at 78.

¹⁴ Michael Livermore, Allen B. Riddell, and Daniel N. Rockmore, *The Supreme Court and the Judicial Genre*, 59 *ARIZ. L. REV.* 837 (2017), at 863.

¹⁵ Blei, *supra* note 10, at 78; Livermore, Riddell, and Rockmore, *supra* note 14, at 864.

¹⁶ See for an illustration of the topic detection process using an example from a legal corpus: Tobias Gump & Marc Pierre Schneider, *Methoden der künstlichen Intelligenz in der Rechtswissenschaft*, 1 *ZEITSCHRIFT FÜR DIGITALISIERUNG UND RECHT* 155 (2021), at. 160-161.

take metadata, such as authors of documents or timestamps,¹⁷ into account.¹⁸ Document preprocessing includes the removal of stopwords and other words that appear too frequently in the corpus to provide semantic information.¹⁹ Rare words are also typically excluded, both because they cannot be usefully allocated by frequency and in order to lower computational cost.²⁰ Furthermore, documents may be shuffled.²¹

II. Application to Legal Research

The result of this process is a list of topics which can be used as a classifier of documents by topics and may provide a basis for further corpus exploration.²² More generally, topic models can assist in quantitatively examining the semantic features of (legal) corpora.²³ Legal studies involving topic models usually report the list of topics identified by the algorithm and labeled by lawyers. While some focus on the technical aspects of the process,²⁴ others use the results for more specific research questions. For example, *Law* examines 171 preambles of constitutions and international human rights instruments to find evidence of “constitutional archetypes” underlying these documents.²⁵ Assuming a “liberalist”, a “statist”, and a “universalist” archetype, the author first generates models of three, four and ten topics and considers the three topic model to best fit the corpus, whereas in a four-topic-model, the “universalist” archetype is represented by two topics.²⁶ While both the “liberalist” and the “statist” topic appear to be connected with characteristic vocabulary, this does not seem to be the case for the “universalist” archetype. The author further examines correlations between the predominant “archetype” of a constitution and variables such as its origin (“newer” state, human rights instrument), legal system (civil law, common law, authoritarian) or characteristics of a fundamental rights catalogue.²⁷

Livermore et. al., in their study of the genre of the US Supreme Court Decisions, use topic modeling to compare the distribution of 100 topics in Supreme Court opinions with those in Appellate Court opinions, and to examine which topics are correlated with the grant of certiorari and whether differences in semantic content are changing over time.²⁸ The authors show that topic distributions of Supreme Court decisions and the corresponding Appellate Court decisions are more similar than those of Supreme Court decisions and 10.000 random Appellate Court decisions.²⁹ They conclude that Supreme Court opinions are measurably distinct compared to Appellate Court decisions, that a correlation between topic proportions

¹⁷ Margaret E. Roberts, Brandon M. Stewart, and Dustin Tingley, *Stm: An R Package for Structural Topic Models*, 91 (2) JOURNAL OF STATISTICAL SOFTWARE 1–40 (2019), DOI: 10.18637/jss.v091.i02; R Core Team, *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*, 2019, <https://www.R-project.org/> (last visited Aug 26, 2021).

¹⁸ Blei, *supra* note 10, at 83.

¹⁹ David J. Carter, James Brown, and Adel Rahmani, *Reading the High Court at a Distance: Topic Modelling the Legal Subject Matter and Judicial Activity of the High Court of Australia*, 39 UNIVERSITY OF NEW SOUTH WALES LAW JOURNAL 1300 (2016), at 1311; Yannis Panagis & Evangelos Sakkopoulos, *Scaling Out to Become Doctrinal*, in ALGORITHMIC ASPECTS OF CLOUD COMPUTING: SECOND INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP, ALGOCLOUD 2016, AARHUS, DENMARK, AUGUST 22, 2016, REVISED SELECTED PAPERS (Timos Sellis & Konstantinos Oikonomou eds., 2017), DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-57045-7_10, at 163; YLJA REMMITS, FINDING THE TOPICS OF CASE LAW: LATENT DIRICHLET ALLOCATION ON SUPREME COURT DECISIONS (2017), <https://theses.uhn.ru.nl/handle/123456789/5218>, at 8 (last visited Aug 26, 2021).

²⁰ Since words in corpora are distributed in a Zipf- or power law-distribution (LNRE: large number of rare events), this is not without problems: Using only the 10 000 most frequent lexemes, which is the amount that can be handled by the R stm package, leaves out another 58 000 in our FCC corpus.

²¹ Carter, Brown, and Rahmani, *supra* note 19, at 1312.

²² Blei, *supra* note 10, at 79.

²³ Livermore, Riddell, and Rockmore, *supra* note 14, at 863.

²⁴ See generally Panagis & Sakkopoulos, *supra* note 19; Remmits, *supra* note 19.

²⁵ David Law, *Constitutional Archetypes*, 95 TEX. L. REV. 153, at 194.

²⁶ Law, *supra* note 25, at 196.

²⁷ Law, *supra* note 25, at 208–210.

²⁸ Livermore, Riddell, and Rockmore, *supra* note 14, at 842–843.

²⁹ Livermore, Riddell, and Rockmore, *supra* note 14, at 870.

and the likelihood of a grant of certiorari exists and that Supreme Court opinions become more distinctive over time when measured against federal appellate cases.³⁰

In a study of the issue content of ECJ decisions, *Dyèvre and Lampach* create separate models for infringement and annulment rulings (assuming 15 topics) and preliminary references (25 topics),³¹ and visualize the resulting topics as networks. An examination of the development of topics over time provides results that are evaluated to be “in line with the dominant narratives of the European integration process in EU studies”³² such as a decline of “constitutional” topics in preliminary reference documents. Issue attention in infringement cases is considered to vary less than in annulment or referral cases.³³ In order to validate their topic model, the authors relate it to a citation network of manually collected decisions on family reunion cases and come to the conclusion that higher centrality in the citation network correlates with higher topic proportion.³⁴

Carter and Rahmani use Topic Modeling to track the development of two specific legal doctrines in judgments of the High Court of Australia. The authors create models consisting of 10 and 20 topics and visualize the topic weights in a number of judgments related to the doctrines in question (and selected in accordance with traditional legal methods) in order to analyze the evolution of topic content in these cases.³⁵ Furthermore, they show the positions of the selected judgments in a network of the dominant topics of all judgments in the corpus.³⁶

In the context of German Law, recent work by *Gumpp and Schneider* creates a topic model of the entire German statutory law consisting of 30 topics, employs network analysis to visualize stronger and weaker connections between the statutes belonging to a certain area of law and discusses possible uses of topic modeling for research on the system of legal principles, sources of inspiration for analogous application of laws and guiding principles for potential codifications of areas of law.³⁷

III. Challenges

This short introduction to topic modeling and its application to legal research questions has already hinted at some of the methodological challenges involved with this approach:

The assumption that documents are a “bag of words” in which the order of words does not matter is unrealistic.³⁸ So is the assumption that the order of the documents in the corpus is irrelevant. It may be contested whether topics are truly static, particularly if the corpus spans several decades.³⁹ Adaptations of LDA have been developed to resolve these issues.⁴⁰ Documents may be randomly shuffled to avoid a bias towards earlier cases.⁴¹ However, this does not resolve the fundamental problem that probabilities – and thus statistics over word distributions – must be doubted on a conceptual level: Over time, new words are coined, changing the relative frequency of all words to appear in the corpus, new discourses will develop,

³⁰ Livermore, Riddell, and Rockmore, *supra* note 14, at 872–878.

³¹ Arthur Dyèvre, and Nicolas Lampach, *Issue Attention on International Courts: A Text-Mining Approach*, <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3251186> (2019), at 21 (last visited Aug 26, 2021).

³² Dyèvre & Lampach, *supra* note 31, at 36.

³³ Dyèvre & Lampach, *supra* note 31, at 37.

³⁴ Dyèvre & Lampach, *supra* note 31, at 41.

³⁵ David J. Carter & Adel Rahmani, *Proximity and Neighbourhood: Using Topic Modelling to Read the Development of Law in the High Court of Australia*, 45 MONASH UNIVERSITY LAW REVIEW 785 (2020), at 813.

³⁶ Carter and Rahmani, *supra* note 35, at 817.

³⁷ Tobias Gumpp & Marc Pierre Schneider, *supra* note 16.

³⁸ Blei, *supra* note 10, at 82.

³⁹ Blei, *supra* note 10, at 82.

⁴⁰ Cf. Yannis Panagis, Martin Lolle Christensen, and Urška Šadl, *On Top of Topics: Leveraging Topic Modeling to Study the Dynamic Case-Law of International Courts*, in LEGAL KNOWLEDGE AND INFORMATION SYSTEMS (Floris Bex & Serena Villata, eds., 2016), 161–166, where Non-Negative Matrix Factorization is used to create “dynamic topics” of CJEU case-law.

⁴¹ Carter, Brown, and Rahmani, *supra* note 19, at 1312.

bringing with them a terminology that is more diverse at the beginning, before being subject to a certain degree of standardization.⁴²

Composition and pre-processing of the corpus or of various subcorpora are, of course, areas for dispute that should be resolved with the research question in mind. Furthermore, some court-specific words do not serve the purpose of distinguishing between documents because they occur too frequently.⁴³ Excluding these words should prevent topics that consist of words like *judgment*, *statute*, *law* or the name of the court – words that, at first sight, can appear in any document and are not distinctive of a particular topic. However, in contrast to language-specific stopwords that will be frequent in any corpus, court-specific words might in fact be more frequent in some documents than in others and thus might indeed characterize a topic.⁴⁴

The number of topics is determined either by choice of the researcher, or algorithmically through statistical pre-processing. The assumption that this number is known and fixed is unrealistic. *Law* assumed three constitutional archetypes and concluded that this number leads to more convincing topic compositions than four or ten topics,⁴⁵ however, due to the non-deterministic algorithm, this result might be different in a new calculation. In other research setups, the number of topics may vary between different time periods and depend on the changing amount of cases and the broadening area of competence of the courts.⁴⁶ For their choice of topic numbers, *Dyevre and Lampach* relied on the interpretability of the topics and the number of documents in their subcorpora, resulting in different amounts of topics for different types of procedures.⁴⁷ The unsupervised topic modeling algorithm has no sense of what a meaningful topic is and is given no definition.⁴⁸ Setting the number of topics too low may result in topics that are too general and appear throughout the corpus, setting it too high may lead to “topics lacking enough contextual markers to provide a clear sense of how the topic is being expressed in the text”.⁴⁹ Consequently, *Carter et. al.* find that their 20-topic model is marked by greater granularity than the model for 10 topics.⁵⁰ This may lead to topics that are less interpretable and therefore less useful for humans.⁵¹ To avoid having to guess a number of topics, one may apply algorithms which automatically determine the number of topics.⁵² While this yields *statistically* better partitions, the interface to linguistics is entirely undefined: There exists no linguistically motivated, scalar, quantitative model of what constitutes a topic and which (if any) quantitative markers, such as specifiable frequencies of word co-occurrence, would clearly demarcate topic boundaries. Thus, even the best statistical model cannot be shown to correspond to an ideal linguistic model of a topic.⁵³ This is further implied in the statement that the choice between a higher and a lower number of topics yields topics of varying granularity. While there may exist subcategories of meaningful granularity, at present, there are no best practices to decide whether a chosen number of topics adequately represents subject-specific topics of interest.

⁴² For an in-depth discussion see Shadrova, *supra* note 6.

⁴³ For example, Carter & Rahmani, *supra* note 35, at 802, removed words which appear in more than half of the judgments.

⁴⁴ Shadrova, *supra* note 6, at 9-10.

⁴⁵ *Law*, *supra* note 25, at 198 (fn. 160).

⁴⁶ Panagis & Sakkopoulos, *supra* note 19, at 163.

⁴⁷ Dyevre & Lampach, *supra* note 31, at 21.

⁴⁸ MATTHEW L. JOCKERS, *MACROANALYSIS: DIGITAL METHODS AND LITERARY HISTORY* (2013), at 123.

⁴⁹ Jockers, *supra* note 48, at 128.

⁵⁰ Carter & Rahmani, *supra* note 35, at 820; for a previous comparison of a 10- and 50-topic model for the High Court of Australia corpus: Carter, Brown, and Rahmani, *supra* note 19, at 1329.

⁵¹ Jonathan Chang, Jordan Boyd-Graber, Chong Wang, et al., *Reading Tea Leaves: How Humans Interpret Topic Models*, 22 *ADVANCES IN NEURAL INFORMATION PROCESSING SYSTEMS*, VOL. 22 (Yoshua Bengio, Dale Schuurmans, John Lafferty et al., eds. 2009), at 6.

⁵² Blei, *supra* note 10, at 83.

⁵³ Shadrova, *supra* note 6.

Furthermore, researchers have to decide which topic model to use, depending on the data and the research questions.⁵⁴ While Latent Dirichlet Allocation is common, other algorithms also exist.⁵⁵ When interpreting the results, it should be taken into account that Latent Dirichlet Allocation is not deterministic. Running the same algorithm on the same corpus repeated times may lead to different results depending on the starting point (word or document) of the algorithm, which contradicts the idea of an ‘ideal’ model and escapes validation through sampling due to the staggering number of possibilities (the varying number of plausible topic numbers multiplied by the number of seeds, that is points of initialization of the algorithm).

Finally, the interpretability and coherence of the resulting topics may be questioned.⁵⁶ Providing a label may not capture every dimension of the topic itself.⁵⁷ While studies often report that labels are intuitively interpretable and match traditional legal categories,⁵⁸ there are approaches to empirically validate the coherence and interpretability. Examples include the classification of documents on the basis of topic proportions and using labels provided by human readers as categories,⁵⁹ comparing the topic model to a citation network of manually collected decisions,⁶⁰ and having human subjects evaluate the coherence of the most probable words for each topic.⁶¹ In a non-legal context, *Chang et al.* conducted large-scale experiments on how humans interpret the semantic coherence of topics and their representation in documents for three different models.⁶² In order to evaluate topic coherence, the test subjects were presented with six words, of which five were the most probable words from a randomly chosen topic and the sixth was a randomly chosen word with a low probability in that topic but high probability in some other topic.⁶³ Whether the models’ assignments of topics to documents are consistent with human judgments was measured by presenting the title and a snippet from a document along with four topics associated with this document and one topic chosen randomly from the remaining topics.⁶⁴ The authors come to the conclusion that “humans appreciate the semantic coherence of topics and can associate the same documents with a topic that a topic model does” while traditional metrics for topic evaluation do not capture whether topics are coherent or not.⁶⁵

Despite these uncertainties, topic modeling is widely used, and with the growing availability of large datasets is likely to become more widely used, in the social sciences. Leaving some of these aspects unaddressed, we will first present results from a topic model based on a corpus of FCC decisions and then provide an example of how topic modeling can be used as a pre-processing tool in a computer-assisted hermeneutic approach to hypothesis-based analysis of large text data.

IV. A Topic Model of the FCC’s Official Report Series

When topic modeling is applied to legal corpora, an obvious approach is to choose a number of topics, report the word clusters generated by the topic modeling algorithm and label them according to traditional doctrinal ideas of areas of law or subjects of legal disputes. Recognizable patterns are easily found. We generated a topic model of the decisions published in the official report series of the FCC between 1951 and 2017. In order to avoid bias when interpreting the list of topics, we asked a small number of colleagues, all familiar with the FCC’s decisions (using a written catalogue of questions) about what topics they expect

⁵⁴ Blei, *supra* note 10, at 83; Remmits, *supra* note 19, at 3.

⁵⁵ Such as Non-Negative Matrix Factorization (NMF), *see generally* Panagis, Christensen, and Šadl, *supra* note 40; Carter & Rahmani, *supra* note 35, at 798, relied on NMF for a more specific research question, in contrast to the use of LDA for a previous, more general overview of the Australian High Court’s work in Carter, Brown, and Rahmani, *supra* note 19.

⁵⁶ Jockers, *supra* note 48, at 128.

⁵⁷ Carter, Brown, and Rahmani, *supra* note 19, at 1317 (fn. 87), admitting that for some topics they would prefer not to provide a label.

⁵⁸ Dyeve & Lampach, *supra* note 31, at 26; more restrictively: Livermore, Riddell, and Rockmore, *supra* note 14, at 893.

⁵⁹ Livermore, Riddell, and Rockmore, *supra* note 14, at 869.

⁶⁰ Dyeve & Lampach, *supra* note 31, at 41.

⁶¹ Remmits, *supra* note 19, at 11; Carter & Rahmani, *supra* note 35, at 804.

⁶² Chang et al., *supra* note 51.

⁶³ Chang et al., *supra* note 51, at 3.

⁶⁴ Chang et al., *supra* note 51, at 4.

⁶⁵ Chang et al., *supra* note 51, at 8.

to appear and how these topics will develop over time. The answers were hardly comparable, which shows that the concept of what constitutes a topic is by no means unambiguous. However, some common ideas emerged: Inter alia, topics concerning *Europe, equality* (general⁶⁶ and gender-equality⁶⁷), *religion, freedom of expression, technology and data protection/privacy rights* and *democracy* were expected, as well as a rise in prevalence of the topics *Europe, equality* and *technology/data protection*.

Our corpus of Federal Constitutional Court decisions comprises 9.267 decisions published between 1951 and 2017. For this analysis, we use only decisions published in the official report series (3308). A number of court-specific words and some linguistic artifacts were removed.⁶⁸

In what follows in this section, we used the *stm* package in *R* with the number of topics set to 25.⁶⁹ The distribution of topics is deterministic in this case, because the initialization of the model was based on *Arora et al.'s* spectral algorithm.⁷⁰ The results are shown in Fig. 1 (displayed are the five most frequent and exclusive words, i.e., words that occur in only one topic – reported as *frex*) and 2 (five most frequent words, i.e., words may overlap between topics). All words are set to lowercase in the analysis and will be reported as such.

⁶⁶ Article 3 (1) Basic Law.

⁶⁷ Article 3 (2) and (3) Basic Law.

⁶⁸ Stopwords: *dass, satz, antragsgegnerin, gesetzgeber, verfassungsbeschwerde, sollen, antragsgegner, recht, verfahren, entscheidung, müssen, landgericht, oberlandesgericht, gericht, grundrecht, bundesverfassungsgericht, bundesgerichtshof, beschwerdeführerin, beschwerdeführer, wegen, datum, fall, entscheidung, recht*. We also removed some abbreviations (*gg, abs, art, vgl, nr*) and nonwords occurring due to tokenization issues.

⁶⁹ Roberts, Stewart, and Tingley, *supra* note 17; R Core Team, *supra* note 17. While we explored models with 50 and 100 topics, as is also suggested for larger corpora in the package vignette, those models did not appear to provide access to a layer of topics of higher granularity, but rather appeared to introduce more randomness and uninterpretable topics. Whether a number of topics ≥ 100 would yield better results remains for future research.

⁷⁰ See generally Sanjeev Arora, Rong Ge, and Ankur Moitra, *New Algorithms for Learning Incoherent and Overcomplete Dictionaries*, 35 PROCEEDINGS OF MACHINE LEARNING RESEARCH 779–806 (2014). The algorithm decides on the ideal initialization point for the statistically best partition into n topics – in our case, 25 – through a Non-Negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) before performing the topic modeling.

Top Topics

Fig. 1: A topic model of the official report series for 25 topics (frequent and exclusive – frex).

Fig. 2: A topic model of the official report series for 25 topics (most frequent words).

We find that, when representing topics by the five most frequent words, topics more often seem to be made up of general words that may appear in different contexts in an FCC decision. The frex words give more specific hints. However, in some cases looking at the frequent words in addition to the frex words can help in interpreting the topic content.

We find topics associated with

- Europe: topic 21 (frex: member state, european, central bank – freq: german, treaty),
- religion: topic 25 (frex: religious education, school prayer, head scarf – freq: church, religious),
- freedom of expression: topic 8 (frex: press freedom, novel, freedom of expression, freedom of artistic expression, work of art – freq: expression, public, general),

- technology/data protection: topic 19, (frex: surveillance of the home, file, informational, stored – freq: stpo⁷¹).

As expected, topic prevalence for topic 19 (data protection) and topic 21 (Europe) increases over time (fig. 3 and 4).

Fig. 3: Development of topic 19 (data protection) over time.

⁷¹ Abbreviation for the code of criminal procedure (*Strafprozessordnung*).

Fig. 4: Development of topic 21 (Europe) over time.

There is no topic that is obviously concerned with *democracy* as such, although some aspects of the principle of democracy may be represented in topic 5, which seems to relate to elections (frex: overhang mandate, electoral equality, constituency, electoral complaint – freq: Bundestag, election, party, deputy) and possibly topic 15, which might relate to political parties’ right to be equally represented in broadcast (frex: broadcasting time, freedom of broadcasting – freq: political party, political, broadcast, public). Likewise, it is difficult to find an *equality* or *gender equality* topic. However, questions of equal treatment may concern a wide range of subject matters, such as (apart from the aforementioned electoral equality) family law, which is represented by topic 10 (frex: illegitimate, paternity, civil partnership, parent – freq: child, spouse, marriage, mother) or tax law, with which topic 20 is concerned (frex: taxable person, rateable value, estg,⁷² taxation, income tax – freq: income, fiscal).

While the most frequent topic, topic 6, contains words of a more general character, the second-most frequent topic (topic 4) seems to be related to the criminal procedure (defense counsel, public prosecution office, main hearing, accused person).⁷³ Words related to the enforcement of the sentence (frex: preventive detention, coercive treatment, imprisonment, punishment, prisoner) seem to cluster in topic 17. For technical reasons, 14 documents had been missing in this initial exploration. They have been included in a new model, which can be found in Appendix section I.1. This second model, although based on almost the same data, provided remarkably different results. The proportions, order (in terms of proportionality) as well as the composition of the topics is different. In the new model, when looking at the 5 most frequent

⁷² Abbreviation referring to the income tax code (*Einkommensteuergesetz*).

⁷³ Constitutional complaints against decisions by criminal courts make up for 26% of all constitutional complaints between 1991 and 2017: Federal Constitutional Court, *Annual Statistics 2017*, https://www.bundesverfassungsgericht.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/EN/Statistik/statistics_2017.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=4, at 23 (last visited Aug 26 2021).

and exclusive words, topic 19 appears to deal with data protection (surveillance of the home, privacy of telecommunications, Federal Intelligence Service), however, it appears to be interwoven more strongly with criminal law (preventive detention, prisoner) than in the first model, where more general words such as file, informational, and stored appear among the 5 most frequent and exclusive words. Indeed, when taking the 5 most frequent words into account, topic 19 appears to be mainly relating to criminal law. Furthermore, while in the first model the five most frequent words in topic 16 appeared to relate to communism and thus, possibly, to the decision which banned the Communist Party of Germany (KPD),⁷⁴ no such topic can be found in the new models. This exemplifies that automatically generated topic models can react sensitively to minor changes in the data.

Our corpus exploration has shown the difficulties in defining what constitutes a topic and in interpreting a computer-generated topic structure. Therefore, we intend to use topic modeling only as a first step in order to define topic terms we are interested in.

C. Comparing Areas of Law in Different Types of Proceedings

In this section, we will investigate the areas of law represented in constitutional complaints and referrals for judicial review. First of all, we will give an overview of the different types of proceedings in German constitutional procedure (section I) which is the foundation for our hypotheses (section II). Afterwards, we will explain our research methods (section III) and present the results (section IV) before undertaking a follow-up investigation into sub-areas of private law (section V).

I. German Constitutional Procedure

The German Federal Constitutional Court (FCC) does not form part of the regular court system in Germany. In contrast to the U.S. Supreme Court, its jurisdiction is strictly limited to matters of constitutional law. Accordingly, legal remedies to the FCC are restricted to a numerus clausus of types of proceedings. These proceedings differ, inter alia, concerning the initiating party and the scope of protection. Furthermore, they involve differing prerequisites with regards to, for example, prior review by ordinary courts or time-limits for commencing proceedings. We will analyze only two types of proceedings: constitutional complaints and referrals for judicial review. This is motivated primarily by the fact that both constitutional complaints and referrals for judicial review may concern an equally wide range of questions of constitutional law – for reasons that will be outlined below – while other types of proceedings often pertain to specific constitutional provisions, such as electoral rights (electoral complaints), separation of powers (*Organstreit* proceedings) or the prohibition of political parties. Consequently, it is to be expected that subcorpora of these latter types of proceedings will be primarily concerned with these specific legal issues. The second, more practical, reason for limiting our analysis to only two types of proceedings is the representation of the different proceedings in the corpus. While not all decisions on constitutional complaints have been published,⁷⁵ they nevertheless dominate the official report series (1935 out of 3308, 58%). Referrals for judicial review of statutory law are the second most common type of proceeding before the FCC. They account for 25% of the cases in our corpus (817 out of 3308). In addition, there are 66 cases in which constitutional complaints and referral for judicial review have been joined (2%).

1. Constitutional Complaints

Constitutional complaints⁷⁶ can be initiated by any natural or legal entity that claims a violation of her fundamental rights. Rather strict procedural prerequisites counterbalance the large number of potential

⁷⁴ 5 BVERFG 85, which is the second longest decision of the FCC.

⁷⁵ Constitutional complaints account for approximately 97% of the Court's caseload (224.221 of 232.089), Federal Constitutional Court, *supra* note 73, at 1; however, only a minority of these applications are admitted for decision and of those, only a minority – mainly decisions by the senates – appears in our corpus.

⁷⁶ Article 93 (1) No. 4a of the Basic Law.

complainants: generally speaking, a constitutional complaint will only be heard after legal protection has been refused by the ordinary courts. A complainant must demonstrate that she has exhausted any regular legal remedy before filing a constitutional complaint. Accordingly, constitutional complaints are usually directed against the final decision of a regular court, which – according to the complainant – is in breach of the Constitution (*Urteilsverfassungsbeschwerde*). Here, the complainant will regularly base her complaint on one of the following arguments: either, she will argue that the (last-instance regular) court violated her fundamental rights because, in her specific case, it applied a law in an unconstitutional way, e.g. by misbalancing the affected constitutional interests; or she may claim that the statutory law itself that governs her case may be unconstitutional. In this latter case, the complainant formally directs her complaint against a court decision, but indirectly accuses Parliament of an unconstitutional act. Hence, the FCC will indirectly control the constitutionality of statutory law, and, as a consequence, it may invalidate such a law, when it finds its provisions to be in violation of the Constitution.⁷⁷

Under specific and exceptional conditions, the FCC does, however, hear cases that directly target statutory law (*Rechtssatzverfassungsbeschwerde*) and in which the complainant is not obliged to first seek legal protection from the regular courts. These cases include complaints against statutory authorization of clandestine measures that typically go unnoticed⁷⁸ (e.g. secret surveillance by police authorities) as well as provisions concerning fines or punishments.⁷⁹ The constitutional complaint can only be lodged within a month after the last-instance court decision (*Urteilsverfassungsbeschwerde*) or a year after the promulgation of the challenged law (*Rechtssatzverfassungsbeschwerde*).⁸⁰

It thus appears that the FCC is rather easily accessible by way of constitutional complaints. A large number of complaints is however filtered by the Court's relatively harsh admissibility tests.⁸¹ Notably, complainants must sufficiently substantiate their complaints in order to be heard before the FCC. This threshold can actively be used by the Court to limit its caseload, as it provides the justices with certain procedural leeway when assessing a complaint.⁸² Moreover, about 99% of constitutional complaints have lately been referred to chambers of three rather than the full senate of eight justices.⁸³ Since chamber decisions have been systematically published only from 1998 on, we restrict our investigation to those decisions that have been published in the Official Report Series.⁸⁴

2. Referrals for Judicial Review

Referrals for judicial review⁸⁵ can be initiated by any court, consequently, the group of possible initiators, although smaller than in the case of constitutional complaints, is still large compared to other types of proceedings. Whenever a court is convinced of the unconstitutionality of statutory law or the incompatibility of state law with federal law which is relevant to a specific case on its docket, it is obliged to suspend the proceedings and ask for a preliminary ruling by the FCC. Thus, referrals for judicial review

⁷⁷ § 95 (3) second sentence of the Act on the Federal Constitutional Court (*Bundesverfassungsgerichtsgesetz, BVerfGG*). For a quantitative analysis of alleged and actual violations of fundamental rights in decisions based on constitutional complaints see Luisa Wendel, *Welche Grundrechte führen zum Erfolg?*, 75 JURISTENZEITUNG 668–679 (2020).

⁷⁸ See 133 BVERFGE 277 (311-312).

⁷⁹ See Bundesverfassungsgericht [BVerfG] [Federal Constitutional Court], 72 NEUE JURISTISCHE WOCHENSCHRIFT 659 (2019).

⁸⁰ See § 93 BVerfGG.

⁸¹ For a critical assessment see Herbert Bethge, § 90, in BUNDESVERFASSUNGSGERICHTSGESETZ – KOMMENTAR (Theodor Maunz, Franz Klein, Herbert Bethge et al., eds., 57th edition, 2019), at 124a.

⁸² Cf. Frank Schorkopf, *Die Prozessuale Steuerung des Verfassungsrechtsschutzes: Zum Verhältnis von materiellem Recht und Verfassungsprozessrecht*, 130 ARCHIV DES ÖFFENTLICHEN RECHTS (2005) 465, at 475 and 489–90.

⁸³ Matthias Jestaedt, *Phänomen Bundesverfassungsgericht. Was das Gericht zu dem macht, was es ist*, in DAS ENTGRENZTE GERICHT: EINE KRITISCHE BILANZ NACH SECHZIG JAHREN BUNDESVERFASSUNGSGERICHT (Matthias Jestaedt, Oliver Lepsius, Christoph Möllers, and Christoph Schönberger, eds., 2011) 79, at 115.

⁸⁴ Apart from senate decisions, the Official Report Series also contains a small number of plenary and chamber decisions.

⁸⁵ Article 100 (1) Basic Law. Other translations of *konkrete Normenkontrolle* include *specific judicial review of statutes*, see Federal Constitutional Court, https://www.bundesverfassungsgericht.de/EN/Verfahren/Wichtige-Verfahrensarten/Konkrete-Normenkontrolle/konkrete-normenkontrolle_node.html (last visited Aug 26, 2021) or *concrete judicial review*, see Federal Ministry of Justice, http://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/englisch_gg/englisch_gg.html (last visited Aug 26, 2021).

regularly occur at an earlier stage than the constitutional complaint: constitutional complaints may – for the most part – only be filed after exhausting all regular legal remedies, whereas referrals for judicial review take place as an extraordinary intermediate step during regular proceedings. As a prerequisite, the law in question must have been enacted after the Basic Law entered into force in 1949.⁸⁶ This is because Article 100 (1) Basic Law intends to protect the legislation passed by the democratic legislator, however, courts may disregard unconstitutional laws predating the Basic Law since in such cases, no protection is necessary. As opposed to constitutional complaints, referrals for judicial review are not subject to any time limits.

Similarly to the constitutional complaints, the FCC has established strict requirements for the admissibility of referrals for judicial review, particularly concerning the interpretation of the requirement that the regular court's decision depend on the validity of the law. The referring court must substantiate its reasons to refer the law to the FCC in a comprehensible way⁸⁷ and these reasons must not be “manifestly untenable”⁸⁸. These requirements provide the FCC, to some extent, with a rather flexible instrument to control its caseload⁸⁹ and possibly also the choice of subject matter.⁹⁰ A decision notably does not depend on the validity of the law if the law can be interpreted or developed in a way that is in compliance with the constitution.⁹¹ In practice, half of the referrals are considered to be inadmissible.⁹²

II. Hypotheses

In light of the abovementioned, should we expect notable differences in topic prevalence between the two types of proceedings? On a purely conceptual level, the coverage of issues should be nearly identical, not least since in both types of proceedings, admissibility criteria allow the FCC a certain flexibility in accepting cases. If the case is admissible, the FCC performs a full-fledged fundamental rights analysis.⁹³ This includes questions of a mere *formal* constitutionality of statutory law (i.e. federal vs. state competences, observance of the legislative process etc.) in both proceedings.⁹⁴ Therefore, the applicable constitutional law is basically the same in both types of proceedings.⁹⁵

Nevertheless, we expect significant empirical deviations between the thematical issues covered by both types of proceedings: Apart from seeing topics that concern the different procedural requirements of both proceedings, we expect a clear overrepresentation of issues concerning social law, tax law and civil service law in decisions on referrals for judicial review. Conversely, we expect cases that deal with free speech, the general personality right, data protection, EU Law, criminal and private law to mostly occur in constitutional complaints.

⁸⁶ Joachim Wieland, *Art. 100*, in GRUNDGESETZ KOMMENTAR: BAND III ARTIKEL 83-146 (Horst Dreier, ed., 3rd ed., 2018), at 12.

⁸⁷ 88 BVERFGE 198 (201).

⁸⁸ 138 BVERFGE 1 (15)

⁸⁹ Schorkopf, *supra* note 82, at 475; Wieland, *supra* note 86, at 12.

⁹⁰ Werner Heun, *Richtervorlagen in der Rechtsprechung des Bundesverfassungsgerichts*, in VERFASSUNG UND VERFASSUNGSGERICHTSBARKEIT IM VERGLEICH (Werner Heun, ed., 2014) 165, at 175; this is also indicated by UWE KRANENPOHL, HINTER DEM SCHLEIER DES BERATUNGSGEHEIMNISSES: DER WILLENSBILDUNGS- UND ENTSCHEIDUNGSPROZESS DES BUNDESVERFASSUNGSGERICHTS (2010), at 119 (Interview 6).

⁹¹ Jan-R. Sieckmann & Sibylle Kessel-Wulf, *Art. 100*, in V. MANGOLDT/KLEIN/STARCK GRUNDGESETZ – KOMMENTAR, VOL. 3 (Peter M. Huber & Andreas Voßkuhle, eds., 7th ed., 2018), at 39.

⁹² CHRISTIAN HILLGRUBER & CHRISTOPH GOOS, VERFASSUNGSPROZESSRECHT (4th ed., 2015), at 573; Rüdiger Zuck, *Die Wissenschaftlichen Mitarbeiter des Bundesverfassungsgerichts*, in Das BUNDESVERFASSUNGSGERICHT IM POLITISCHEN SYSTEM (Robert Chr. Van Ooyen & Martin H.W. Möllers, eds., 2006) 283, at 290, argues that the FCC “successfully eliminated” the referral proceedings.

⁹³ The constitutional law standards the FCC applies to the case do not depend on the type of proceeding, see Oliver Lepsius, *Entscheiden durch Maßstabbildung*, in HANDBUCH BUNDESVERFASSUNGSGERICHT IM POLITISCHEN SYSTEM (Robert Chr. van Ooyen & Martin H. W. Möllers, eds., 2nd ed., 2015) 119, at 133.

⁹⁴ Cf. 6 BVERFGE 32 (41).

⁹⁵ One conceptual difference worth mentioning here concerns the question of entitlement to fundamental rights, which corresponds to the right to file a constitutional complaint. Certain public entities as well as non-EU legal persons may not lodge a constitutional complaint, whereas they may still initiate a regular court proceeding that can lead to a referral. However, even here, the content issues at stake are not necessarily dependent on the extent to which the parties involved are themselves entitled to fundamental rights.

The reasons for our expectations are twofold: they include considerations as to the asynchronicity of both types of proceedings as well as structural specifics in the respective areas of law that form the subject of the proceeding.

1. Asynchronicity

We believe that the different actors that may initiate the two types of proceedings as well as the time of their initiation directly impact the structure of the content issues. Recall that referrals are embedded in the regular court proceedings, whereas the constitutional complaint predominantly succeeds regular court proceedings: Local courts, state courts, and federal courts are all entitled to refer a question of the constitutionality of a statute to the FCC. Accordingly, in a three-instance court proceeding, a total of three courts have the opportunity to challenge the constitutionality of a law before a constitutional complaint can be filed by the individual citizen, since – for the most part – constitutional complaints require the exhaustion of all legal remedies including second and third instance appeals.

The referral may thus be considered a first turnoff to the FCC, which can only be taken by the courts. Once this path has been chosen, the room for subsequent constitutional complaints by the involved private parties is substantially reduced. When substantiating her allegation of a fundamental rights violation, the complainant must engage with the standards previously developed by the FCC.⁹⁶ If the FCC, on the occasion of a referral for judicial review, found that a statutory provision is compatible with the Basic Law, a subsequent constitutional complaint must meet even higher standards and therefore is rather unlikely to be admissible.

Conversely, we expect constitutional complaints to mostly occur in view of topics that strike private individuals (and their respective lawyers) as constitutionally problematic, but not the courts. As a result, issues will largely be left over for constitutional complaint proceedings in three constellations: first, the complainant believes that the regular courts' specific application of statutory law is unconstitutional. Second, she is convinced that the statutory law that governs her case is unconstitutional, while the courts disagreed and, therefore, abstained from referring the question to the FCC. Or third, by way of exception, a constitutional complaint can be filed without a prior call of the regular courts (*Rechtssatzverfassungsbeschwerde*), hence, allowing for constitutional complaints without even a theoretical possibility of a referral for judicial review.

Taking this asynchronicity of referrals for judicial review and constitutional complaints into account, we expect an uneven thematic distribution in both types of proceedings:

We believe areas of law that are highly specific, rather instable and, therefore, not long established under judicial law to be especially prone to referrals for judicial review, because they are characterized by a large number of very particular statutory regulations and a high frequency of amendments to the law. This applies, for example, to *social, tax, and civil service law*.⁹⁷ As a result, qualitative scholarly law literature widely laments a “lack of consistent systematics” in these areas.⁹⁸ We believe that such an instability of the written law encourages regular court judges to doubt the constitutionality of the respective sectoral legislation. In contrast to this, we expect the topics of *freedom of expression* as well as matters of (general)

⁹⁶ 130 BVERFG 1 (21).

⁹⁷ DIETER BIRK, MARC DESENS, AND HENNING TAPPE, *STEUERRECHT* (22nd ed., 2019), at 27; on the role of social welfare and tax law for the growing complexity of law, see Daniel Martin Katz, Corinna Coupette, Janis Beckedorf, and Dirk Hartung, *Complex Societies and the Growth of the Law*, 10 SCIENTIFIC REPORTS 18737 (2020).

⁹⁸ Birk, Desens, and Tappe, *supra* note 97, at 27. AXEL KOKEMOOR, *SOZIALRECHT* (8th ed., 2018), at 9, characterizes the evolution of social law in Germany as a “bit by bit development without any integrated concept”; Helmut Lecheler, § 110 *Der öffentliche Dienst*, in *HANDBUCH DES STAATSRECHTS DER BUNDESREPUBLIK DEUTSCHLAND*, VOL. 5 (Josef Isensee & Paul Kirchhof, eds., 3rd ed., 2007) 559, at 577, describes civil service law as a “multitude of detailed regulations”; Peter Badura, *Art. 33*, in *MAUNZ/DÜRIG, GRUNDGESETZ – KOMMENTAR* (Rupert Scholz, Matthias Herdegen, and Hans H. Klein, eds., 2020) at 76-77, points to the reformation of civil service law as a “permanent task” of the political bodies, emphasizing divergent concepts in the legislative efforts of the German states (Länder) in fleshing out the specifics of German civil service law.

criminal and private law to be overrepresented in constitutional complaints. Private and criminal law are characterized by a higher stability of the statutory law and even its respective legal doctrine. Hence, we expect courts to be much less in doubt as to the constitutionality of the underlying statutory law, which we believe to be predominantly perceived as well-trying and long-settled. If constitutional problems arise in these areas, we rather assume them to be framed as problems of an incorrect application of statutory law in the individual case.⁹⁹ Thus, in criminal law, for example, we would not expect many referrals for judicial review by the criminal courts concerning the constitutionality of the abstract penal provisions, but rather subsequent constitutional complaints of convicts regarding the application of the penal provisions in their individual cases.

Finally – particularly in certain areas of *data protection law* and *constitutional law of the European Union*, but also in criminal law – the direct path to a constitutional complaint is opened much sooner by way of the *Rechtssatzverfassungsbeschwerde*. In these cases, it is not necessary to first initiate a regular court proceeding and consequently, there will be fewer situations in which a regular court might refer a question of constitutionality to the FCC. We expect FCC decisions relating to these areas of law to originate in constitutional complaints rather than referrals for judicial review.

The flowchart in fig. 5 gives a (simplified)¹⁰⁰ overview of the different ways by which a statutory provision pertaining to a specific area of law may become the subject of a referral for judicial review or a constitutional complaint, thus contributing to one of the subcorpora.

⁹⁹ In particular when balancing the specific interests at stake, such as, on the one hand, freedom of expression and, on the other hand, personality rights.

¹⁰⁰ The simplification concerns the following aspects: *Proceedings in regular court* may concern, for example, private lawsuits, criminal trials or administrative litigation and may be preceded by administrative action applying the law. Regular court proceedings may involve several instances, a referral may be initiated on each level. If a constitutional complaint challenges only the application of the law, the statutory provision in question and its corresponding area of law may still constitute a topic of the resulting decision. Referrals or constitutional complaints that are being treated by a chamber instead of a senate and are not published in the Official Report Series will not be part of our subcorpora.

Fig. 5: Overview of possible paths by which a law (here: a statutory provision) may end up in one of the subcorpora (simplified, see fn. 100).

2. Structural Specifics

Secondly, for areas of law that are increasingly open to interpretation, especially through general clauses, we expect a significantly greater presence in the subcorpus of constitutional complaints. We assume that topics related to private law will occur much less in referrals, for the higher frequency of general clauses as well as the horizontal relationship between the private parties presumably yield a larger scope of interpretation than in other areas of law. This gives the judge more leeway for construing a statutory provision in accordance with the Constitution and, thus, prevents her from having to refer the case to the FCC. Again, the individual parties may not agree with such a harmonization of the statutory law with the Constitution by the regular court judges and file constitutional complaints. Consequently, while we expect much fewer referrals for judicial review in areas of law that are characterized by increased interpretive room of manoeuvre, we do not believe this to confine constitutional complaints.

3. Areas of Law

In the present investigation, we are using the term *area of law* and have chosen several particular areas for a closer examination. We are aware that they differ in size, that they may occupy different levels in a hierarchical order of areas of law and that they may overlap.

It might appear desirable to develop a definition of the term area of law and a comprehensive taxonomy. However, within the scope of this study, this is neither feasible nor necessary. There have been several attempts to define the term area of law in the literature.¹⁰¹ However, there are no universal, objective criteria for deciding whether a set of rules constitutes an area of law – rather, these depend on historical, political and other circumstances,¹⁰² and are the subject of a complex process of interaction between the legislator, legal scholars and other members of the legal profession.¹⁰³ We therefore use the term somewhat casually in correspondence with our hypotheses, which do not call for a highly specific differentiation of potentially ambiguous cases.

Our choice of areas of law follows our hypotheses. It is by no means incontestable. One may question, for example, whether an area of law such as freedom of expression is of the same status or significance as criminal law or social law and how to deal with the intersections it inevitably forms with private, criminal, or other areas of law.¹⁰⁴ The First Senate of the FCC, in its decision on the internal allocation of proceedings to reporting Justices, chose to explicitly allocate proceedings concerning the “freedom of expression, information, broadcasting and the press” to a specific Justice – which indicates that constitutional court practice warrants a delimitation of this area of law.¹⁰⁵ In a similar vein, the Second Senate of the FCC allocated “proceedings from all areas of law” which predominantly concern the interpretation and application of article 23 – and, therefore, questions concerning the limits of European Integration – to a

¹⁰¹ For possible approaches see Ines Härtel, *Energieeffizienzrecht - Ein neues Rechtsgebiet?*, 33 *Natur und Recht* 825 (2011), at 827; Wolfgang Winkler, *Landwirtschaftsrecht: Ausnahmerecht oder besonderes Rechtsgebiet? – Dargestellt am Beispiel des Verhältnisses zwischen Bürgerlichem Recht und Landwirtschaftsrecht*, in REICHWEITE UND GRENZEN DES AGRARRECHTS – GEDÄCHTNISCHRIFT FÜR DR. WOLFGANG WINKLER (José Martínez, ed. 2018) 249, at 261. Rejecting the existence of an area of law due to a lack of system-building common features: PETER AXER, *DIE WIDMUNG ALS SCHLÜSSELBEGRIFF DES RECHTS DER ÖFFENTLICHEN SACHEN: ZUR IDENTITÄT DES RECHTS DER ÖFFENTLICHEN SACHEN ALS RECHTSGEBIET* (1994) at 22, 223. Indeed, it is not uncommon for German legal literature to employ the term area of law (*Rechtsgebiet*) without further definition, see for example Rüdiger Zuck, *Biomedizin als Rechtsgebiet*, 26 *MEDIZINRECHT* 57 (2008), at 57.

¹⁰² Härtel, *supra* note 101, at 827.

¹⁰³ Michael Stolleis, *Wie entsteht ein Wissenschaftszweig? Wirtschaftsrecht und Wirtschaftsverwaltungsrecht nach dem Ersten Weltkrieg*, in *UMWELT, WIRTSCHAFT UND RECHT* (Hartmut Bauer, Wolfgang Kahl, Andreas Voßkuhle et al., eds., 2002) 1, at 10.

¹⁰⁴ Such as the law of civil servants where the freedom of expression of civil servants is concerned.

¹⁰⁵ The same can be argued for data protection law, which is, however, split and allocated to several Justices. For the allocation of subject areas in 2020 see the overview at Federal Constitutional Court, Overview of the allocation of proceedings within the First Senate,

https://www.bundesverfassungsgericht.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/DE/GV_2020/GV_2020_S1_II_Anlage.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=2 (last visited Aug 26, 2020).

specific reporting Justice.¹⁰⁶ The apparent expediency of aggregating these proceedings in a single department indicates that EU constitutional law can be considered an area of law for the purposes of this study.

That being said, in the course of our examination, it became apparent that comparing a small area of law such as freedom of expression with a considerably bigger, more comprehensive area such as private law might lead to results that are difficult to interpret. We therefore developed and tested more precise hypotheses relating to private law below in section V.

III. Methods

We first compiled the subcorpora of constitutional complaints (marked by a file number containing the letters *BvR*) and referrals for judicial review (marked by *BvL*). Since our corpus includes decisions in cases where constitutional complaints and referrals for judicial review have been joined according to § 66 BVerfGG, a third subcorpus containing only these decisions was created in order to avoid artifacts stemming from duplicate data and thus lower-than-actual differentiation between proceedings. However, only 66 decisions in the corpus stem from joined *BvR/BvL* proceedings compared to 1935 decisions from *BvR* only proceedings and 817 decisions from *BvL* proceedings.¹⁰⁷ We removed some court-specific words as well as some linguistic artifacts from pre-processing.¹⁰⁸

We then computed separate topic models for each of the subcorpora. The number of topics was chosen algorithmically through an optimization function provided by the spectral initialization as provided in the algorithm by *Arora et al.*¹⁰⁹ ($k=0$ flag in the *stm* package). Thus, unlike in the previous analysis, where the number of topics was set to 25, in this analysis, not only the best initialization point for a partition into n topics was algorithmically determined, but also the statistically overall best partition was computed. This was done in hope of extracting topic numbers that are better suited for the large size difference between subcorpora. However, despite the size difference of factor 2.3 between the two major subcorpora, the number of automatically extracted topics was nearly identical at 92 vs. 95. Even in the small subcorpus containing only 65 joined case proceedings, the automatic extraction still yielded 78 topics.

Due to some earlier technical issues, this initial exploration was performed under exclusion of 13 relevant documents. We report the topic models generated for the incomplete subcorpora since these were the basis for the following word selection process. The final analysis (see section IV) includes all 2818 documents pertaining to the two types of proceedings.

Figures 6, 7, and 8 show the expected topic proportions. Remarkably, the topics with the highest expected topic proportions both for the constitutional complaint subcorpus and the referral for judicial review subcorpus seem to concern questions of admissibility. Among the ten most frequent and exclusive words in the relevant topic 45 for constitutional complaints are words such as *rechtsweg* (recourse to the courts), *verwerfen* (dismiss) and *unzulässig* (inadmissible). The respective topic 32 for referrals for judicial review includes *vorlage* (referral), *unzulässig* (inadmissible) and *verfassungsmäßigkeit* (constitutionality). The subcorpus of joined proceedings contains no topic dealing with inadmissibility, which is not surprising given that proceedings may be joined only when they are admissible.¹¹⁰ In order to circumvent some of the epistemological uncertainty that was discussed above, we then proceeded with a modified methodology

¹⁰⁶ Federal Constitutional Court, Overview of the allocation of proceedings within the Second Senate, https://www.bundesverfassungsgericht.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/DE/GV_2020/GV_2020_S2_II_Anlage.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=5 (last visited Aug 26, 2020).

¹⁰⁷ In both subcorpora, a decision might concern joined proceedings of another type than *BvL/BvR*, such as *Organstreit* proceedings.

¹⁰⁸ Stopwords: *dass, satz, antragsgegnerin, gesetzgeber, verfassungsbeschwerde, sollen, antragsgegner, recht, verfahren, entscheidung, müssen, landgericht, oberlandesgericht, gericht, grundrecht, bundesverfassungsgericht, bundesgerichtshof, beschwerdeführerin, beschwerdeführer, wegen, datum, fall, entscheidung, recht*. We also removed some abbreviations (*gg, abs, art, vgl, nr*) and nonwords occurring due to tokenization issues.

¹⁰⁹ See generally Arora, Ge, and Moitra, *supra* note 70.

¹¹⁰ 12 BVERFGE 205 (223); 106 BVERFGE 210 (215)

compared to the previous analysis: Using topic modeling solely as a pre-processing tool to yield all relevant variants of the variables relevant to our hypothesis, i.e. the words occurring under labels such as *social law* or *EU constitutional law*, we then performed an exact keyword search in the corpus. This process circumvents the insecurity from the lack of a topic definition and the lack of a functional interface between lexical co-occurrence and statistics (we define the topic through terms we consider relevant from an expert stance), and fuzzy topic boundaries (we perform an exact keyword search and no longer need to rely on topic prevalence estimations). The complexity as well as the argument is thus shifted back from the heuristic approach to the expert understanding of the subject, i.e. the plausibility of the topics and their variables. At the same time, the topic model serves a genuine purpose in yielding the variants necessary for our search, thus providing a type of structured exploration or heuristic pre-processing; where the latter is not dissimilar from a hermeneutic approach involving close-reading, but is now applicable to much larger data thanks to the use of text mining techniques such as topic modeling.¹¹¹

¹¹¹ A combination of automated extraction of frequent and distinctive words and qualitative decisions taken by researchers has been employed by Annie Waldherr, Lars-Ole Wehden, Daniela Stoltenberg, et al., *Induktive Kategorienbildung in der Inhaltsanalyse: Kombination Automatischer und manueller Verfahren*, 20 (1) FORUM: QUALITATIVE SOZIALFORSCHUNG (2019) Art. 19, to inductively generate a hierarchical system of categories from free text answers in an online survey.

Normenkontrolle (exklusiv), automatische Topiczahl, frex

Fig. 7: A topic map of referrals for judicial review in the official report series (free and exclusive words – frex), excluding decisions about joined constitutional complaints and referrals for judicial review, algorithmically calculated number of topics.

nur kombiniert, automatische Topiczahl, frex

Fig. 8: A topic model of joined constitutional complaints and referrals for judicial review in the official report series (frequent and exclusive words – frex), algorithmically calculated number of topics.

The necessity for methodological extension is further corroborated by the fact that the initial computation from 2808 documents yields somewhat surprisingly divergent results compared to the model based on 2818 documents.¹¹² While we are confident that central terms relevant to the areas of law chosen for our analysis were present in both, especially since the added documents make up less than 0.5% of the total corpus, the divergent numbers of topics (92 vs. 86 for referrals and 78 vs. 86 for the combined proceedings) as well as the differences in topic rank and word distributions per topic show the extreme sensitivity of statistical word-to-topic allocation. This lack of robustness of the method to derive conceptual topics from highly similar data underlines our point that topic modeling cannot be expected to produce reliable results valid for scholarly argumentation and should only be used as a tool for exploration and an aid in extracting candidates for further analysis.

In a first step, three legal scholars independently identified the automatically generated topics related to the hypotheses and labeled them with higher-order labels such as *private law* or *social law* (see tab. 1), and a label *miscellaneous* for topics that were not clearly identifiable or not of interest for the present investigation. The labels were then discussed and final labels were agreed upon. Finally, for each of the topics grouped under a label, we selected those words out of the 10 most frequent and exclusive topic words that we considered relevant for the label, thus removing intruder words and adding relevant words from the miscellaneous topic, if necessary.¹¹³ The chosen terms were then used as keywords for an exact search of the subcorpora.

Table 1: Labels for manual annotation of topics and number of selected words

<i>German</i>	<i>English</i>	<i>Number</i>
Beamtenrecht	civil service law	29
Datenschutzrecht	data protection law	9
EU-Verfassungsrecht	EU constitutional law	11
Zivilrecht	private law	116
Sozialrecht	social law	70
Steuerrecht (Abgabenrecht)	tax law and law relating to other fiscal duties	65
Strafrecht	criminal law	81
Meinungsfreiheit	freedom of expression	11

As can be seen from tab. 1, labels subsume word sets of rather diverse size. This is in part due to differences in the granularity of the considered higher-order topics (such as private law vs. EU constitutional law), and partially an effect of the diversity and relevance of those topics in the context of the FCC. Where this interferes with direct comparability between categories, it will be discussed alongside the results.

¹¹² Which can be found in Appendix section 1. For example, in the new model, the composition and proportions of the three biggest topics in constitutional complaints has changed notably and the word *unzulässig* (inadmissible) is not included anymore. Rather, the most frequent topic includes names of months (*februar, april*) and the abbreviation *gez.*, referring to the Justices' signatures at the end of the decision.

¹¹³ At this stage, one lawyer selected words for private law, while the other two selected words for all other areas of law.

IV. Results

1. Prevalence of Topic Terms

We begin by assessing the prevalence of topic terms for each subcorpus. If the listed terms are comprehensively relevant to the respective type of proceedings, the number of frequently appearing terms should be high. Considering the different sizes of the subcorpora and the power-law distribution of words,¹¹⁴ it must be assumed that the number of frequent terms will be different for each subcorpus. Figures 9 – 12 show the number of terms per topic that occur ≥ 5 , ≥ 10 , ≥ 20 and ≥ 50 times in the respective subcorpus.

	const. complaint	joined	referral for jud. review
<i>civil service law</i>	28	15	29
<i>criminal law</i>	80	49	68
<i>data protection law</i>	9	2	3
<i>EU constitutional law</i>	11	7	8
<i>freedom of expression</i>	11	2	8
<i>private law</i>	112	73	110
<i>social law</i>	65	39	67
<i>tax law</i>	57	25	56

Fig. 9: Number of terms per topic occurring 5 times or more per subcorpus.

	const. complaint	joined	referral for jud. review
<i>civil service law</i>	28	9	29
<i>criminal law</i>	80	46	64
<i>data protection law</i>	9	0	0
<i>EU constitutional law</i>	11	5	8
<i>freedom of expression</i>	11	1	7
<i>private law</i>	111	69	103
<i>social law</i>	58	35	67
<i>tax law</i>	53	20	55

Fig. 10: Number of terms per topic occurring 10 times or more per subcorpus.

¹¹⁴ See generally GEORGE KINGSLEY ZIPF, *THE PSYCHO-BIOLOGY OF LANGUAGE. AN INTRODUCTION TO DYNAMIC PHILOLOGY*. 1935 (1965). Some more recent research suggests that words may not actually be distributed by Zipf's law (see generally Jake R Williams, Paul R Lessard, Suma Desu, et al., *Zipf's Law Holds for Phrases, Not Words*, 5 SCIENTIFIC REPORTS Art. 12209 (2015); Laurence Aitchison, Nicola Corradi, and Peter E Latham, *Zipf's Law Arises Naturally When There Are Underlying, Unobserved Variables*, 12 PLOS COMPUTATIONAL BIOLOGY Art. e1005110 (2016); Steven T Piantadosi, *Zipf's Word Frequency Law in Natural Language: A Critical Review and Future Directions*, 21 (5) PSYCHONOMIC BULLETIN & REVIEW 1112 (2014). Even so, it is clear that word distributions are marked by large numbers of rare events (see generally HARALD R BAAYEN, *WORD FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTIONS* (2001); STEFAN EVERT, *THE STATISTICS OF WORD COOCCURRENCES: WORD PAIRS AND COLLOCATIONS* (2005), <https://elib.uni-stuttgart.de/handle/11682/2573> (last visited Aug 26, 2021).

	const. complaint	joined	referral for jud. review
<i>civil service law</i>	27	5	29
<i>criminal law</i>	79	31	56
<i>data protection law</i>	9	0	0
<i>EU constitutional law</i>	10	3	8
<i>freedom of expression</i>	11	0	5
<i>private law</i>	108	58	97
<i>social law</i>	54	31	63
<i>tax law</i>	50	12	49

Fig. 11: Number of terms per topic occurring 20 times or more per subcorpus.

	const. complaint	joined	referral for jud. review
<i>civil service law</i>	24	0	24
<i>criminal law</i>	76	15	45
<i>data protection law</i>	9	0	0
<i>EU constitutional law</i>	10	2	8
<i>freedom of expression</i>	11	0	3
<i>private law</i>	92	37	75
<i>social law</i>	43	13	59
<i>tax law</i>	42	6	39

Fig. 12: Number of terms per topic occurring 50 times or more per subcorpus.

From these results it can be concluded that the selected terms are indeed relevant. Even in the subcorpus of joined proceedings, which contains only 66 documents, half of the selected terms or more for civil service law, EU constitutional law, criminal law and private law appear at least 5 times. This may not seem much, however, even in the largest corpora, more than half of all lemmata are *hapax legomena*, i.e., words that occur only once in the corpus.¹¹⁵ While the topic modeling is based only on words that occur somewhat frequently, and rare words are explicitly filtered out, we later combined terms from different models that would not necessarily be expected to occur equally in all subcorpora. For the two larger subcorpora, there is little difference between the numbers for terms appearing at least 5 times and for terms appearing at least 10 times, apart from data protection law vanishing from the results for the referrals subcorpus.

The numbers of topic terms that appear at least 50 times in the subcorpora for constitutional complaints on the one hand and referrals for judicial review on the other hand begin to diverge. Criminal law is represented by considerably fewer terms in the referral subcorpus than in the constitutional complaints subcorpus (45 vs. 76), whereas social law is represented by remarkably more terms in the referral subcorpus (59 vs. 43), which is particularly notable considering that the constitutional complaints subcorpus contains more than twice as many documents as the referrals subcorpus. Overall, the analysis indicates that the selected terms are sufficiently frequent, procedure-specific and relevant. It thus appears that topic models are useful as a fuzzy search tool for unknown variants, not yielding too many false positives when combined with an expert screening.

Referrals for judicial review are the second most frequently initiated type of proceeding in the FCC, but they still amount to less than half as many documents compared to the subcorpus of constitutional complaints. The power-law distribution of words implies that the frequency of terms does not scale linearly. This means

¹¹⁵ See generally Janet Pierrehumbert & Ramon Granell, *On Hapax Legomena and Morphological Productivity*, in PROCEEDINGS OF THE FIFTEENTH WORKSHOP ON COMPUTATIONAL RESEARCH IN PHONETICS, PHONOLOGY, AND MORPHOLOGY 125 (2018), doi: 10.18653/v1/W18-5814.

that a corpus that is 2.3 times the size of a smaller corpus will not contain 2.3 times the number of all terms of the smaller corpus. Instead, some words will be saturated both in the smaller and the larger corpus (hapaxes that remain hapaxes), some frequent words will gain in absolute numbers, and many new hapaxes are expected to occur in the larger corpus. There exists no best practice on what to expect in terms of frequency distributions, since words are by definition an open class (new ones can be and are frequently created in a process termed *productivity* in linguistics), and the use of words is obviously sensitive to factors such as language change, topic, register (situation or context and degree of formality), etc. This makes it difficult to compare corpora of different sizes in terms of the lexical exemplars they contain.¹¹⁶ To be sure that comparable numbers in the two corpora reflect actual differences rather than saturation effects, we compared ten samples of 200 documents each from both subcorpora. Obviously, in the smaller subcorpus, the number of overlapping documents between samples is higher.

Figs. 13 – 16 confirm that results are robust for equal-sized samples. Relevantly, they confirm our hypothesis that while all topics *can* and *do* appear in both types of proceedings, the *internal distribution* of topics is divergent: In referrals, for most samples, the ratio of frequent criminal law terms and frequent private law terms is between 1:2 and 3:5 and the ratio of frequent social law terms and frequent private law terms is about 2:3 to 1:1. In constitutional complaints, approximately the same number of criminal law terms and private law terms appears frequently in each sample, whereas noticeably less social law terms and civil service law terms appear when compared to private law terms. It follows that, while there are not significantly fewer (probably even more) frequent private law terms in referrals for judicial review compared to constitutional complaints, the ratio within each subcorpus is in line with our hypotheses: tax law, social law and civil service law terms are – relative to private law terms – more frequent in decisions on referrals for judicial review.

	sample_1	sample_10	sample_2	sample_3	sample_4	sample_5	sample_6	sample_7	sample_8	sample_9
<i>civil service law</i>	25	24	24	24	26	26	27	24	26	27
<i>criminal law</i>	51	54	50	53	51	49	47	52	53	50
<i>data protection law</i>	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
<i>EU constitutional law</i>	8	8	6	7	7	7	7	6	8	7
<i>freedom of expression</i>	1	3	3	5	3	5	6	3	2	6
<i>private law</i>	76	85	75	76	88	75	84	81	85	78
<i>social law</i>	56	49	54	52	48	56	49	54	53	55
<i>tax law</i>	45	47	41	36	44	32	42	46	42	42

Fig. 13: Number of topic terms occurring 5 or more times in samples of 200 texts: Referrals for judicial review

	sample_1	sample_10	sample_2	sample_3	sample_4	sample_5	sample_6	sample_7	sample_8	sample_9
<i>civil service law</i>	18	18	18	20	17	22	23	16	21	22
<i>criminal law</i>	36	38	31	34	29	31	29	32	31	30
<i>EU constitutional law</i>	4	7	5	7	6	4	4	3	7	7
<i>freedom of expression</i>	1	1	2	1	2	2	3	0	1	2
<i>private law</i>	51	54	49	47	56	59	52	50	59	52
<i>social law</i>	38	32	38	39	29	41	32	39	38	35
<i>tax law</i>	30	28	28	25	30	25	27	27	28	29

Fig. 14: Number of topic terms occurring 20 or more times in samples of 200 texts: Referrals for judicial review

¹¹⁶ Morphosyntactically motivated categories of words appear to be more comparable, see ANNA SHADROVA, MEASURING COSELECTIONAL CONSTRAINT IN LEARNER CORPORA: A GRAPH-BASED APPROACH (2020), doi: 10.18452/21606.

	sample_1	sample_10	sample_2	sample_3	sample_4	sample_5	sample_6	sample_7	sample_8	sample_9
<i>civil service law</i>	19	19	19	20	19	22	21	18	21	16
<i>criminal law</i>	57	61	66	61	65	61	64	63	62	63
<i>data protection law</i>	1	6	7	6	6	2	6	6	4	5
<i>EU constitutional law</i>	10	8	9	7	10	7	9	7	7	7
<i>freedom of expression</i>	8	9	10	11	8	9	8	11	6	11
<i>private law</i>	72	74	85	73	59	84	83	73	76	64
<i>social law</i>	27	30	28	21	22	31	28	28	27	30
<i>tax law</i>	39	32	35	31	29	28	28	24	26	24

Fig. 15: Number of topic terms occurring 5 or more times in samples of 200 texts: Constitutional complaints

	sample_1	sample_10	sample_2	sample_3	sample_4	sample_5	sample_6	sample_7	sample_8	sample_9
<i>civil service law</i>	4	10	9	9	15	12	15	14	9	8
<i>criminal law</i>	39	45	44	36	53	42	58	50	44	45
<i>data protection law</i>	0	2	7	2	2	0	5	2	1	4
<i>EU constitutional law</i>	9	6	9	3	9	6	9	5	6	5
<i>freedom of expression</i>	5	7	6	7	7	6	6	7	4	7
<i>private law</i>	39	46	62	39	39	48	56	41	50	44
<i>social law</i>	15	15	14	11	10	16	14	12	14	15
<i>tax law</i>	21	20	23	22	20	19	20	17	17	13

Fig. 16: Number of topic terms occurring 20 or more times in samples of 200 texts: Constitutional complaints

For better comparison between samples, figs. 17 and 18 show heatmaps, where red tiles indicate higher provenance of terms in constitutional complaints, while purple tiles indicate higher provenance in referrals for judicial review. Again, the plots show clear tendencies for terms from data protection law, freedom of expression, and slightly less for criminal law to be more provenant in the constitutional complaints subcorpus, and for social law, tax law, and civil service law to be more provenant in the referrals subcorpus.¹¹⁷

¹¹⁷ Larger differences between samples indicate a higher specialization of terms: They tend to occur in bundles and only in some documents. If those documents are not included in the sample, only few or even none of the terms occur (as in the case of data protection law in fig. 17, samples 3, 6, and 7).

Number of terms occurring 5 times or more in samples:
Const. complaints divided by referrals for jud. review

Fig. 17: Ratio of the number of terms under the respective labels that occur 5 or more times in samples of 200 documents, number of terms in constitutional complaint subcorpus samples divided by number of terms in the referral for judicial review subcorpus samples. 'Inf' indicates zero terms with a frequency of 5 or higher in the referrals.

Fig. 18: Ratio of the number of terms under the respective labels that occur 20 or more times in samples of 200 documents, number of terms in constitutional complaint subcorpus samples divided by number of terms in the referral for judicial review subcorpus samples. 'Inf' indicates zero terms with a frequency of 20 or higher in the referrals sample. Missing values indicate zero terms with a frequency of 20 or higher in either subcorpus.

To recapitulate the main hypotheses:

- H_0 : No difference in the frequency of occurrence of topic-relevant terms by subcorpus
- $H_{1_1} - H_{1_3}$: for civil service law, tax law, social law: frequency of occurrence in referrals for judicial review > constitutional complaints
- $H_{2_1} - H_{2_5}$: for private law, freedom of expression, data protection law, European constitutional law, criminal law: frequency of occurrence in referrals for judicial review < constitutional complaints

One-sided paired t-test statistics were computed on the mean frequency of each term across ten 200-text-samples. Relative frequencies from the whole corpus were not used due to the difference in size (817 vs. 1935 documents in the two subcorpora). Since word frequencies do not scale linearly, a simple division by number of documents would have skewed the results. The paired test was used, because more frequent terms in general can also be expected to be more frequent in both subcorpora, effectively forming pairs. This yielded the following results:

Table 2: One-sided paired t-test over mean frequencies of terms across 10 200-text samples. CC = Constitutional Complaint, RJR = Referral for judicial review.

<i>Area of Law</i>	<i>Hypothesis</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Confirmed?</i>
civil service law	H1_1: f(RJR) > f(CC)	-3.7874	<0.001	confirmed
criminal law	H2_5: f(RJR) < f(CC)	4.7444	<0.001	confirmed
data protection law	H2_3: f(RJR) < f(CC)	5.3055	<0.001	confirmed
EU constitutional law	H2_4: f(RJR) < f(CC)	1.5416	n.s. (0.0771)	n.s.
freedom of expression	H2_2: f(RJR) < f(CC)	2.3052	0.0219	confirmed
private law	H2_1: f(RJR) < f(CC)	-0.68859	n.s. (>0.75)	n.s.
tax law	H1_2: f(RJR) > f(CC)	-2.2037	0.0154	confirmed
social law	H1_3: f(RJR) > f(CC)	-4.3147	<0.001	confirmed

While these results confirm our hypotheses in major aspects, they should be viewed with caution: It appears that there is a tendency of topics to be overall more represented in referrals for judicial review compared to constitutional complaints. This effect may stem from the difference in corpus size (less noise or randomness) or it may be structural in the sense that it is possible that there are other systematically diverging topics that fill parts of the distribution in constitutional complaints, but not referrals, and which are not yet considered in our hypotheses. To gain further insight, we performed an analysis over time.

2. Development over time

To see how the prevalence of a topic develops over time it is necessary to first identify a topic. In classic topic modeling, the topic and the words belonging to it are demarcated in a single process. However, since we refrained from working with those topics due to the epistemological concerns discussed earlier, we need a separate definition. Since it is obviously unreasonable to expect *all* words pertaining to a label to occur in a single document, the question is what marks a useful boundary. This is, as has been mentioned earlier, undefined in linguistics: There is no model of what might constitute a ‘topic’ of this kind, and certainly no scalar quantitative model that would define the number of terms, their granularity or proportion. With words being an open class and ‘topic’ a concept with fuzzy boundaries and many possible levels of granularity, it is not to be expected that such a model can be easily developed from within linguistics either. It is possible that subject-internally, topic boundaries can be reasonably defined for various levels of granularity, however, best practices for this do not exist at present to our knowledge. Thus, we limit our definition to the approximation through two lower bounds: One of at least 3 topic-relevant terms in one document; and one of at least 10 topic-relevant terms. In figs. 19 and 20 we present the proportion of documents per type of proceedings that contains at least three and at least 10 terms from the respective labels.

Fig. 19: Proportion of cases that contain at least 3 of the respective topic terms.

Fig. 20: Proportion of cases that contain at least 10 of the respective topic terms. Contains fewer panels because for the smaller areas of law there are no documents that include 10 of their terms.

As we suggested earlier, the plots demonstrate that results from the previous section contradicting our hypotheses largely appear to be artifacts from corpus size or corpus distribution. In this analysis, however,

- $H_{1_1} - H_{1_3}$ for *civil service law, tax law, social law*: frequency of occurrence in referrals for judicial review > constitutional complaints

are clearly confirmed, and increasingly so over time. Out of

- $H_{2_1} - H_{2_5}$ for *private law, freedom of expression, data protection law, European constitutional law, criminal law*: frequency of occurrence in referrals for judicial review < constitutional complaints

freedom of expression and data protection law are clearly more prevalent in constitutional complaints (confirmed). Criminal law is more variable, but still shows a clear, and increasing, tendency to be more prevalent in constitutional complaints (partially confirmed). EU constitutional law is somewhat difficult to interpret, because it appears to have made a shift since roughly the year 2000 and now is somewhat more prevalent in referrals for judicial review, and would have required more fine-grained hypotheses over time. Private law seems to be an entirely different case: Data points converge to 0.9 over time, indicating that in 90% of recent documents from both proceedings, at least three of the private law-labeled terms occur. This suggests that the list of labels contains terms that are not in fact distinctive of private law. It also hints at a potential change in the language of the Court, where some terms that were once more distinctive are now used more widely, particularly so in constitutional complaints (greater slope). This is further corroborated in fig. 20, where ten terms are still covered by 90% of some documents in the private law topic. It appears, however, that 10 terms may be too limiting to see clear results. While not within the scope of this analysis,

it would be interesting to see in future research how many and which terms are best suited to capture (conceptual and subject-specific) topics; and how this may differ between topics.

V. A More Detailed Analysis of Private Law

1. Hypotheses and Methods

We have seen that the list of terms for private law may not be distinctive for this area of law and that ten terms are covered by 90% of some documents in the private law topic. Finding 3 or even 10 out of 116 terms in a document is more probable than finding 3 (or 10) out of 11 or 29 terms. It thus appears useful to divide private law terms into more fine-grained subtopics. According to the hypotheses we outlined above, we expect areas of law to be overrepresented among the referrals for judicial review if they are rather technical and characterized by frequent legislative changes. Areas of law that have changed less frequently and could develop a more settled jurisprudence as well as areas of law where statutes are characterized by a larger scope of interpretation are less likely to be referred to the FCC and will thus be more prominent in the subcorpus of constitutional complaints. The last-mentioned arguments might not be applicable to *all* of private law. *Family Law* and *tenancy law*¹¹⁸ come to mind as two sub-areas of private law in which the fundamental interests at stake may give rise to constitutional litigation and which have undergone substantial and recurring changes since the creation of the civil code (*Bürgerliches Gesetzbuch*, BGB) in the late 19th century.¹¹⁹ In both areas of law, imbalances in negotiating power might lead to an increased relevance of compelling law that cannot be derogated from and which might make it necessary for the judge to refer the question of constitutionality to the FCC. This might be contrasted with cases concerning the *law of (other) obligations* where the aforementioned horizontal relationship is more tangible and where a judge might have more room for interpreting the law in accordance with the constitution. Furthermore, another aspect might influence the probability of a referral and that is the degree of europeanization of the area of law. If an area of law is highly europeanized, questions concerning the validity of a statute might be framed as a question of conformity with European Law and referred to the European Court of Justice for a preliminary ruling (Article 267 TFEU), while constitutional complaints concerning the application of this law might still be admissible. While the full implications of European integration cannot be discussed in this chapter, we expect words concerning *company law* to appear more prominently in the subcorpus of constitutional complaints, since this area of law is highly influenced by European law. Furthermore, we expect *inheritance law*, which has not been subject to many legislative changes, to be more prominent in the constitutional complaints subcorpus as well. We are left with a category of miscellaneous private law terms for which we cannot provide clear hypotheses¹²⁰ due to the diversity of the terms.

Again, three legal scholars independently labelled the former private law terms with these more specific labels and assigned the final categories in a discussion. We excluded 4 words which, after this second discussion, we considered to belong to social law or public law rather than private law.

¹¹⁸ This is particularly the case as far as the lease of residential property is concerned.

¹¹⁹ Elisabeth Koch, *Einleitung zum Familienrecht*, in MÜNCHENER KOMMENTAR ZUM BÜRGERLICHEN GESETZBUCH VOL. 9 (Elisabeth Koch, ed., 8th ed., 2019) at 79; BERNHARD GRAMLICH, MIETRECHT (15th ed., 2019), at V-VI (preface).

¹²⁰ Apart from our earlier tendency to associate private law with constitutional complaints.

Table 3: Labels for manual annotation of sub-areas of private law and number of selected words

<i>German</i>	<i>English</i>	<i>Number</i>
Familienrecht	family law	49
Erbrecht	inheritance law	6
Wohnungsmietrecht	tenancy law (residential)	10
Gesellschaftsrecht	company law	12
ZivilrechtSonstiges	private law (other)	35

2. Results

The numbers of topic terms occurring at least 5 or 10 times per subcorpus is almost identical (fig. 21 and fig. 22). For topic terms occurring at least 20 or 50 times per subcorpus, fig. 22 and 23 show that family law, when compared to other private law, is slightly more prevalent in the referrals subcorpus. This is not the case for tenancy law. Company law also seems to appear more frequently in referrals for judicial review than in constitutional complaints while there is no clear distinction for inheritance law. The samples in figs. 25 to 28 provide a similar result.

	const. complaint	joined	referral for jud. review
<i>company law</i>	11	8	12
<i>family law</i>	48	40	48
<i>inheritance law</i>	6	4	6
<i>private law (other)</i>	33	14	30
<i>tenancy law (residential)</i>	10	7	9

Fig. 21: Number of civil law subtopic terms occurring 5 times or more in the respective subcorpus

	const. complaint	joined	referral for jud. review
<i>company law</i>	11	7	12
<i>family law</i>	48	39	45
<i>inheritance law</i>	6	3	6
<i>private law (other)</i>	32	14	28
<i>tenancy law (residential)</i>	10	6	7

Fig. 22: Number of civil law subtopic terms occurring 10 times or more in the respective subcorpus

	const. complaint	joined	referral for jud. review
<i>company law</i>	11	5	12
<i>family law</i>	47	35	43
<i>inheritance law</i>	6	1	6
<i>private law (other)</i>	31	11	25
<i>tenancy law (residential)</i>	10	6	6

Fig. 23: Number of civil law subtopic terms occurring 20 times or more in the respective subcorpus

	const. complaint	joined	referral for jud. review
<i>company law</i>	10	3	10
<i>family law</i>	41	23	38
<i>inheritance law</i>	6	0	4
<i>private law (other)</i>	24	6	17
<i>tenancy law (residential)</i>	9	5	3

Fig. 24: Number of civil law subtopic terms occurring 50 times or more in the respective subcorpus

	sample_1	sample_10	sample_2	sample_3	sample_4	sample_5	sample_6	sample_7	sample_8	sample_9
<i>company law</i>	10	11	9	10	6	8	7	9	8	6
<i>family law</i>	31	30	37	30	25	37	39	34	36	34
<i>inheritance law</i>	4	4	4	3	2	3	5	3	3	0
<i>private law (other)</i>	19	20	26	21	18	24	21	20	16	20
<i>tenancy law (residential)</i>	8	7	7	8	8	10	8	6	8	5

Fig. 25: Number of civil law subtopic terms occurring 5 or more times in samples of 200 texts: Constitutional complaints

	sample_1	sample_10	sample_2	sample_3	sample_4	sample_5	sample_6	sample_7	sample_8	sample_9
<i>company law</i>	4	7	6	5	3	3	5	4	5	3
<i>family law</i>	19	21	32	18	16	25	26	21	26	26
<i>inheritance law</i>	1	2	3	1	1	0	5	1	1	0
<i>private law (other)</i>	9	11	18	11	14	14	12	10	13	12
<i>tenancy law (residential)</i>	5	4	4	4	5	6	7	4	4	3

Fig. 26: Number of civil law subtopic terms occurring 20 or more times in samples of 200 texts: Constitutional complaints

	sample_1	sample_10	sample_2	sample_3	sample_4	sample_5	sample_6	sample_7	sample_8	sample_9
<i>company law</i>	6	10	8	11	9	9	9	8	10	9
<i>family law</i>	39	37	36	36	40	39	41	37	41	37
<i>inheritance law</i>	4	5	5	2	5	1	5	6	6	4
<i>private law (other)</i>	17	23	19	20	24	18	19	21	19	19
<i>tenancy law (residential)</i>	7	7	6	4	7	6	6	6	6	6

Fig. 27: Number of civil law subtopic terms occurring 5 or more times in samples of 200 texts: Referrals for judicial review

	sample_1	sample_10	sample_2	sample_3	sample_4	sample_5	sample_6	sample_7	sample_8	sample_9
<i>company law</i>	4	7	7	7	6	8	6	4	8	5
<i>family law</i>	33	27	25	23	31	34	31	25	31	30
<i>inheritance law</i>	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	5	1	0
<i>private law (other)</i>	10	14	12	14	13	11	10	11	14	12
<i>tenancy law (residential)</i>	3	3	3	2	3	5	3	3	3	3

Fig. 28: Number of civil law subtopic terms occurring 20 or more times in samples of 200 texts: Referrals for judicial review

The heatmaps in fig. 29 and 30 also indicate that tenancy law might indeed be more prevalent in the constitutional complaints subcorpus whereas company law (as well as family law) appears more frequently in referrals for judicial review.

Fig. 29: Ratio of the number of terms under the respective labels that occur 5 or more times in samples of 200 documents, number of terms in constitutional complaint subcorpus samples divided by number of terms in the referral for judicial review subcorpus samples

Number of terms occurring 20 times or more in samples:
 Const. complaints divided by referrals for jud. review

Fig. 30: Ratio of the number of terms under the respective labels that occur 20 or more times in samples of 200 documents, number of terms in constitutional complaint subcorpus samples divided by number of terms in the referral for judicial review subcorpus samples. 'Inf' indicates zero terms with a frequency of 20 or higher in the referrals sample. Missing values indicate zero terms with a frequency of 20 or higher in either subcorpus.

Fig. 31: Proportion of cases that contain at least three of the respective topic terms

Fig. 32: Proportion of cases that contain at least five of the respective topic terms

As before, one-sided paired t-test statistics were computed on the mean frequency of each term across ten 200-text-samples. *Civil law (other)* was not tested since no clear hypotheses could be formed due to the high diversity of terms included.

Table 4: One-sided paired t-test over mean frequencies of terms across 10 200-text samples. CC = Constitutional Complaint, RJR = Referral for judicial review

<i>Area of Law</i>	<i>Hypothesis</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Confirmed?</i>
family law	H3_1: f(RJR) > f(CC)	-0.92716	n.s. (0.1792)	n.s.
tenancy law (residential)	H3_2: f(RJR) > f(CC)	2.5686	0.9849	disconfirmed
company law	H4_1: f(RJR) < f(CC)	-1.8983	0.9576	disconfirmed
inheritance law	H4_2: f(RJR) < f(CC)	1.163	n.s (0.1487)	n.s.

Since our hypotheses have not been confirmed, we have to assume that our assumptions about which areas of law give more or less opportunities to initiate a referral are not correct for these areas of private law or that the topic terms chosen do not ideally represent the respective topics. As mentioned above, in particular concepts relating to family law (e.g. marriage, spouse, unmarried)¹²¹ and company law (e.g. management, acquisition, conversion) may be relevant in other areas of law, such as tax law.

D. Conclusion and Future Research

The analysis performed in this study produced outcomes on a number of levels.

Regarding the methodological contribution, we have shown a possible incorporation of topic modeling into the research process: Starting out with well-founded hypotheses, topic modeling was used to productively identify variants of predetermined variables (words pertaining to expert-defined topics). These were then validated by legal experts, thus avoiding the uncertainty of the heuristic procedure in the scholarly argumentation. The prevalence of the topics defined by this process was then examined. In a second iteration of the process, we refined our hypotheses to produce more detailed results. It was also shown that a small-scale comparison, for example through the consideration over time or a sampling to equalize divergent corpus sizes, can help with the validation of unclear results.

The main result of interest to the constitutional lawyer and other observers of the FCC are the differences in topic prevalence in the two subcorpora. There is a tendency of referrals for judicial review to deal with social law, tax law, and civil service law; while constitutional complaints are more likely to treat freedom of expression and data protection. This has been shown in the base topic model, but becomes much more clearly pronounced in the topic-modeling-based exact search of topics as defined by experts, rather than statistically deduced. Results from this analysis confirm the initial hypotheses in most relevant aspects, which is most clearly pronounced in the distribution of topics on proceedings over time. Results suggest with great clarity that, despite the similar scope of protection of the two most relevant types of proceedings, there are quantitative differences in the content issues that reach the FCC, on the one hand, via constitutional complaints and, on the other hand, via referrals for judicial review. While FCC statistics indicate that (between 1991 and 2017) courts concerned with social law and tax law were responsible for 16% and 11%, respectively, of all referrals for judicial review, but only for 7% and 3% of court decisions

¹²¹ Furthermore, *Ehe* (marriage) is, in lowercase, homonym to *ehe* (before).

challenged by constitutional complaints, whereas, for example, criminal law courts initiated 14% of referrals and passed 26% of the challenged decisions,¹²² these statistics do not provide insights about smaller areas of law, such as civil service law.

While our hypotheses were formed based on the characteristics of the different proceedings types and areas of law, the method cannot conclusively provide a causal link between topic prevalence and those characteristics. Other contributing factors may lie in:

- The regular courts' "preferences" in referring questions of constitutionality.
 - Drafting a referral for judicial review means additional work for the judge and the proceedings are stayed until the FCC has reached a decision, which can take years. The admissibility criteria are strict and there is a high risk that the FCC will consider the referral to be inadmissible. Consequently, judges will only refer a question of the validity of a statute to the FCC in exceptional cases.
 - Some courts / jurisdictions may be less overloaded than others or may have more resources in terms of time or personnel. This might make referring a question to the FCC easier for some courts than for others.
 - As far as civil service law is concerned, an additional motivation to refer questions of constitutionality might – in exceptional cases – result from the judge herself being affected by the law in question.¹²³
- The FCCs "preferences" in admitting a constitutional complaint for decision according to § 93a BVerfGG and in deciding whether a decision, in either type of proceeding, should be taken by the senate or chamber.
- Complainants' differing perceptions of fundamental rights violations, as well as differing resources in terms of time and/or money.

The results for the different sub-areas of private law, however, do not confirm our hypotheses. This might be due to specific properties of those areas of private law or to mechanisms of private law litigation which have hitherto not been considered in our model. Furthermore, since our starting point was to dissect our previous topic of private law, the resulting sub-areas might not include an optimal choice of terms. It is also possible that some of the terms pertaining to our private law topic are not particularly salient or distinctive for specific areas of law. This is also suggested by the fact that, in the initial analysis, about 90% of all decisions contained words belonging to private law. More research is needed to resolve this.

Aside from these specific results, our study hints at a number of obstacles a legal researcher wishing to complement her research with quantitative methods might have to overcome: Experienced lawyers may write about areas of law with ease but in order to conduct quantitative research, a researcher must operationalize her research question and find countable proxies for this phenomenon of interest (in this study: keywords validated by constitutional law scholars). The same is, of course, true for other legal concepts that may become the focus of quantitative research. Moreover, we have shown a feasible process for developing testable hypothesis from legal knowledge and dogmatics.

However, our choice of areas of law and their corresponding keywords is not perfect. Some aspects that remain for future research concern the (scholarly) modeling of the topics, i.e. the ontology of the topics chosen. Since topics considered in the analysis are of very different granularity (some contain only 9 terms,

¹²² Federal Constitutional Court, *supra* note 73, at 23, 34.

¹²³ Numerous referrals relating to the remuneration of civil servants have resulted in judgments on very specific provisions: Ulrich Battis, *Rechtssprechungsbericht zum öffentlichen Dienstrecht*, 60 JURISTENZEITUNG 1095 (2005), at 1096.

some over 100), it is justified to ask whether these ‘topics’ are of the same ontological status. This is not simply a pragmatic question, but one that concerns the (implicit or explicit) theoretical model involved: It is possible that some topics of equal size, relevance, or similar jurisprudential categorization are indeed reflected in very different numbers of terms; it is, however, also possible that the categories are not ideally chosen in this regard.

In this context, we also have to take into account that terms may concern more than one area of law. For example, social law and tax law regulate situations that may have been formed by private law, such as families and companies. When defining terms as private law terms, we cannot be sure that they will not appear in larger numbers in some other context. Furthermore, the selection of private law terms, tax law terms etc. in this analysis was done by constitutional lawyers and might differ from what a private law or tax law expert might consider relevant. The choice was made somewhat subjectively. A more objective grouping would require a different approach, such as a survey among lawyers of different specializations.

The strategy outlined in this paper can be used to identify other areas of law and evaluate their prevalence in the FCC corpus or a corpus of decisions of a different court. Our corpus comprised only about 3.000 decisions and it might be more interesting to research the distribution of areas of law, or of another sort of topics, in lower court decisions, of which a much larger number exists but which are much less systematically published. While this remains the case, the FCCs chamber decisions¹²⁴ or the decisions of the Supreme Federal Courts¹²⁵ might form a basis for similar quantitative, text-based research.

¹²⁴ Of which there are more than 6.000.

¹²⁵ Federal Court of Justice, Federal Administrative Court, Federal Finance Court, Federal Labour Court and Federal Social Court, Article 95 (1) Basic Law.

25 topics, highly frequent

Fig. 34: A topic model of the official report series for 25 topics (most frequent words).

II. Terms Used to Describe Areas of Law

Beamtenrecht / civil service law: alimention, altersgeld, amtsbezeichnung, beamtenverhältnis, beamtin, befähigung, beihilfe, berufsbeamtentum, berufssoldat, besoldung, besoldungsgesetz, besoldungsgruppe, bundesbeamte, dienstbezug, dienstherr, dienstverhältnis, dienstzeit, disziplinarverfahren, laufbahn, sbg, staatsdienst, treuepflicht, versorgungsanspruch, versorgungsbezug, versorgungsempfänger, vorbereitungsdienst, waisenrente, wartestand, witwenrente

Sozialrecht / social law: altersrente, altersruhegeld, alterungsrückstellung, arbeitslosengeld, arbeitslosenversicherung, arbeitslosigkeit, arbeitsunfall, ausbildungsförderung, ausgleichsabgabe, bafög, beitragsbemessungsgrenze, beitragsatz, beitragszeit, bestandsrente, bshg, bundesausbildungsförderungsgesetz, bundeserziehungsgeldgesetz, bundessozialgericht, bundesversicherungsanstalt, bundesversorgungsgesetz, bvg, ersatzkasse, erziehungsgeld, existenzminimum, existenznotwendig, festbetrag, fremdrentengesetz, grundrente, halbbelegung, hinterbliebenenrente, invalidenrente, kassenarzt, kassenärztlich, kindergeld, kinderzuschlag, krankengeld, krankenkasse, krankenversicherung, kurzarbeit, lebensbedarf, mutterschaftsgeld, mutterschutz, mutterschutzgesetz, pflegepflichtversicherung, pflegeversicherung, pflichtbeitrag, regelleistung, regelsatz, rente, rentenreformgesetz, rentenversicherung, rentenversicherungsträger, schwerbehinderte, schwerbehindertengesetz, sonderversorgungssystem, sozialgesetzbuch, sozialhilferechtlich, sozialversicherung, sozialversicherungsabkommen, sterbegeld, übergangsgeld, unfallrente, unfallversicherung, verbrauchsstichprobe, versichertengemeinschaft, versicherungskammer, versorgungssystem, waisenrente, wohngeld, wohngeldgesetz

Steuerrecht (Abgabenrecht) / tax law and law relating to other fiscal duties: abgabenerhebung, abgabepflichtige, besteuern, betriebsausgabe, bundesfinanzhof, doppelbesteuerung, einheitswert, einkommenssteuer, einkommensteuergesetz, einkunft, einkunftsart, ergänzungsabgabe, estg, feuerwehlabgabe, finanzamt, finanzgericht, Freibetrag, gewerbesteuer, grundfreibetrag, grundlohn, grundsteuer, hebesatz, investitionshilfeabgabe, kapitaleinkunft, kapitalertrag, kapitalvermögen, kirchensteuer, kirchensteuerpflicht, lag, lastenausgleich, lastenausgleichsgesetz, lohnsteuerjahresausgleich, lohnsteuer-jahresausgleich, lohnsteuerkarte, lohnsummensteuer, mehrwertsteuer, nachsteuer, nettoprinzip, schankerlaubnissteuer, solidarfond, sonderabgabe, sonderausgabe, spielgerätesteuer, steuer, steuerart, steuerberatend, steuerberater, steuerbevollmächtigte, steuerfrei, steuerfreiheit, steuerfreistellung, steuerpflicht, steuersache, steuersatz, umsatzsteuer, umsatzsteuergesetz, unternehmenssteuerrecht, veranlagungszeitraum, vergnügungssteuer, verkehrsteuer, vermögensabgabe, vermögenssteuer, vorsorgeaufwendung, werbungskosten, zweitwohnungssteuer

Datenschutzrecht / data protection law: datenerhebung, gespeichert, informationell, informationstechnisch, rasterfahndung, speichern, speicherung, verbindungsdatum, verkehrsdatum

EU-Verfassungsrecht / EU constitutional law: eugh, ewg, gemeinschaftsrecht, gerichtshof, gouverneursrat, kommission, lissabon, mitgliedstaat, stabilisierungsfond, union, währungsunion

Strafrecht / criminal law: angeschuldigte, auslieferung, auslieferungsersuchen, auslieferungshaft, auslieferungsverfahren, beschlagnahme, beschuldigte, bestrafen, bestrafung, betäubungsmittel, betäubungsmittelgesetz, bewährung, bußgeld, bußgeldbescheid, diebstahl, durchsuchung, durchsuchungsbefehl, durchsuchungsbeschluss, erzwingungshaft, freiheitsentziehung, freiheitsstrafe, gefangene, geldbuße, geldstrafe, geldwäsche, gesamtstrafe, geständnis, haft, haftbefehl, hauptverhandlung, justizvollzugsanstalt, kriminell, lebenslang, maßregel, maßregelvollzug, mindeststrafe, mord, mörder, ordnungswidrigkeit, pflichtverteidiger, resozialisierung, rücklieferung, schöffengericht, schwangerschaftsabbruch, sicherungsverwahrung, staatsanwaltschaft, stpo, strafbar, strafbarkeit, strafbefehl, strafe, straffreiheit, strafgesetz, strafgesetzbuch, strafnorm, strafprozessordnung, strafprozessual, strafsenaat, straftat, straftatbestand, strafverfahren, strafverfolgung, strafvollstreckungskammer, strafvollzug, strafvollzugsgesetz, strafvorschrift, täter, tötung,

unschuldsvermutung, unterbringung, untersuchungsgefangene, untersuchungshaft, verbrechen, verfall, vermögensstrafe, verteidiger, verteidigung, verurteilte, vollzug, wohnraumüberwachung, zwangsbehandlung

Meinungsfreiheit / freedom of expression: bundesprüfstelle, jugendgefährdend, kunstfreiheit, meinungsausßerung, meinungsfreiheit, persönlichkeitsrecht, persönlichkeitschutz, presseerzeugnis, pressefreiheit, privatsphäre, tatsachenbehauptung

Zivilrecht / private law: abgeschiedenheit, abstammung, adoption, aktiengesellschaft, aktienrecht, aktionär, anteilseigner, arbeitsverhältnis, aufgebotsverfahren, aufrechnung, aufsichtsrat, baudarlehen, bauherr, beteiligungserwerb, bgb, ehe, ehedatte, eheliche, ehename, eheweit, eigenbedarf, elterlich, elternrecht, elternschaft, elternteil, erbegemeinschaft, erblasser, erbrecht, erbrechtlich, familiengericht, familienrecht, forderung, geburtsname, geschäftsführung, geschäftsgeheimnis, geschieden, gläubiger, gmbh, güterstand, gwb, hausarbeit, honorar, kapitalgesellschaft, käufer, kaufvertrag, kindererziehung, Kindeswohl, kreditinstitut, kündigungsfrist, lebenspartner, leiblich, leibrente, miete, mieter, mietverhältnis, mietvertrag, mietzins, miterbe, mündel, nachlass, nichtehelich, pächter, pachtverhältnis, pachtvertrag, pachtzins, personengesellschaft, persönlichkeitsrecht, persönlichkeitschutz, pflegekind, privatrecht, rechtsgeschäft, scheidung, scheidungsrecht, schuldner, sorge, sorgerecht, stiefvater, transsexuell, transsexuelle, tsg, umwandlung, unehelich, unterhalt, unterhaltsanspruch, unterhaltspflicht, unterhaltspflichtige, unterhaltsrecht, urheber, urheberrechtlich, urheberrechtsgesetz, uwg, väterlich, vaterschaft, vergleichsmiete, vergleichswohnung, vergütung, verheiratet, vermietet, versicherungsvertrag, versorgungsausgleich, verzinsung, vormund, vormundschaft, vorname, vorstand, vvg, wettbewerber, willensbildung, wohnbedarf, wohnung, wohnungssuchende, zeitgeschichte, zerrüttungsprinzip, zusammenleben

Familienrecht / family law: abstammung, adoption, ehe, ehedatte, eheliche, ehename, eheweit, elterlich, elternrecht, elternschaft, elternteil, familiengericht, familienrecht, geburtsname, geschieden, güterstand, hausarbeit, kindererziehung, Kindeswohl, lebenspartner, leiblich, mündel, nichtehelich, pflegekind, scheidung, scheidungsrecht, sorge, sorgerecht, stiefvater, transsexuell, transsexuelle, tsg, unehelich, unterhalt, unterhaltsanspruch, unterhaltspflicht, unterhaltspflichtige, unterhaltsrecht, väterlich, vaterschaft, verheiratet, versorgungsausgleich, vormund, vormundschaft, vorname, zerrüttungsprinzip, zusammenleben

Erbrecht / inheritance law: erbegemeinschaft, erblasser, erbrecht, erbrechtlich, miterbe, nachlass

Wohnungsmietrecht / tenancy law (residential): eigenbedarf, miete, mieter, mietverhältnis, mietvertrag, mietzins, vergleichsmiete, vergleichswohnung, vermietet, wohnung

Gesellschaftsrecht / company law: aktiengesellschaft, aktienrecht, aktionär, anteilseigner, aufsichtsrat, beteiligungserwerb, geschäftsführung, gmbh, kapitalgesellschaft, personengesellschaft, umwandlung, vorstand

ZivilrechtSonstiges / private law (other): abgeschiedenheit, arbeitsverhältnis, aufgebotsverfahren, aufrechnung, baudarlehen, bauherr, bgb, forderung, geschäftsgeheimnis, gläubiger, honorar, käufer, kaufvertrag, kreditinstitut, kündigungsfrist, leibrente, pächter, pachtverhältnis, pachtvertrag, pachtzins, persönlichkeitsrecht, persönlichkeitschutz, privatrecht, rechtsgeschäft, schuldner, urheber, urheberrechtlich, urheberrechtsgesetz, uwg, vergütung, versicherungsvertrag, verzinsung, vvg, willensbildung, zeitgeschichte